

**THE IMPACT OF GRADE 10 LOCAL SYLLABUS FOR TEACHING
BUDDHISM ON STUDENTS' INTRINSIC ACHIEVEMENTS**

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the work embodied in the thesis was carried out by me in the Faculty of Social Science Arts and Humanities, Lincoln University College. It contains no material previously published or written by another person, except for quotation and summaries which have been dully acknowledged. It has not been submitted for any degree to this university or to any other institution.

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ABSTRACT

This mixed-methods pragmatic educational research investigates the disparity between the goals of the grade 10 Buddhism syllabus in Sri Lankan schools and actual students' outcomes. Despite high exam pass rates, students struggle to apply theoretical knowledge practically, particularly in Vipassana meditation, as emphasized in the Tipitaka. The study aims to evaluate and enhance the effectiveness of the syllabus in fostering intrinsic learning outcomes for grade 10 students. It explores overlooked aspects, pedagogical methods, and philosophical approaches to teaching Buddhism. Guided by the Backward Design Framework, hypotheses address curriculum alignment, student perception, intrinsic achievement factors, and effectiveness enhancement. The methodology uses stratified random sampling and combines quantitative and qualitative data collection methods. The study offers insights into the current curriculum's effectiveness and guides the development of an improved syllabus aligned with learning outcomes. Anticipated implications include pedagogical advancements, curriculum enhancements, better resource allocation, and increased stakeholder cooperation.

Keywords: *Buddhism Curriculum, Teaching Buddhism, Vipassana Meditation, Intrinsic Achievements via Buddhism, Practical Buddhist Studies*

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

G.C.E. : General Certificate of Education

A/L : Advanced Level

O/L : Ordinary Level

ELT: Experiential Learning Theory

ILO: Intended Learning Outcome

ILOs: Intended Learning Outcomes

ILO_Rate: Intended Learning Outcome Rate

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

This inaugural chapter delineates the foundational framework for the research study titled "Examining the Impact of the Current Syllabus for Teaching Buddhism on Students' Intrinsic Achievements of Grade 10." This chapter provides a thorough introduction to the research encompassing the background, prior research, identification of the research gap, articulation of the problem statement, formulation of research aims and objectives, development of research questions, clarification of key terms and assumptions, explication of the methodology, and elucidation of the study's limitations and delimitations. Moreover, the chapter underscores the significance of the outcomes, presents a chapter outline, and concludes with a summary. This comprehensive introduction establishes the necessity, scope, and potential implications of the study within the context of the Sri Lankan education system.

1.1 OVERVIEW

In examining the primary objective of disseminating the Lord Buddha's teachings, it becomes evident that Vipassana meditation occupies a pivotal role within Buddhist praxis. The axiom "The individual who acts according to the Dhamma is protected by the Dhamma itself" underscores the integral nature of Dhamma in influencing both the transcendental (*lokottara*) and secular (*laukika*) dimensions of an individual's existence. The quintessential aim of Buddhism is to shepherd adherents towards Nibbana, the state attained through a progression that begins with moral discipline (*Seela*), advances through concentration (*Samadhi*), and culminates in the realization of eternal bliss, effectively terminating the cycle of reincarnation. The Tripitaka asserts that the Eightfold Path (*Arya Attangika Magga*) constitutes the sole avenue for

achieving “*Nibbana*”. This path is operationalized through the practice of Vipassana meditation, a critical method conspicuously absent from the current Sri Lankan school Buddhism syllabus. The omission or the low level of focus of Vipassana meditation from educational curricula represents a significant lacuna, as this practice is fundamental to the experiential realization of Buddhist doctrinal principles and the ultimate soteriological objective of liberation.

Teachers of Buddhism do not have formal teacher development programmes at a satisfactory level to make their practice be continuous and continual to guide them by the relevant authorized government bodies including the ministry of education. In such a situation, the effectiveness of delivery of Buddhism curriculum is not formally assessed and reported its various aspects to be enriched with newly identified components that are to be added to the next version to raise the contents up. Besides, the perception of the students is not properly recorded. To address these issues, this research is executed with the aim of proposing recommendations for enhancing the effectiveness of teaching Buddhism as a subject to foster intrinsic achievements of learning outcomes dictated in the syllabuses that are to be validated and evaluated as per the content of Tipitaka.

1.2 BACKGROUND

The teachings of Lord Buddha, encapsulated within the Tipitaka, advocate Vipassana as the exclusive technique for attaining liberation from misery through the comprehension of the impermanence of all phenomena. Despite the profound nature of these teachings, their practical application within the Sri Lankan education system, particularly within the Buddhism curriculum, remains notably deficient. Although Buddhism is incorporated into the local school curricula, the pragmatic teaching of

Vipassana and other essential aspects of Buddhist philosophy is conspicuously absent. Let empirical evidence serve as our compass along this uncharted intellectual journey. The Buddha's admonition resonates profoundly: "Do not place trust in anything merely due to its transmission through hearsay. Only after meticulous observation and study should one accept and implement that which aligns with reason and benefits all." In a similar vein, Richard Feynman emphasizes that scientific theories must be grounded in observable, repeatable phenomena rather than conjecture or belief. He asserts, "The elegance of a theory and the intellect behind it are irrelevant; if it does not accord with experimental results, it is incorrect" (Gleick & Dyson, 1992).

Buddhism constitutes a principal subject within the General Certificate of Education Ordinary Level (G.C.E. O/L) curriculum in Sri Lanka. However, obtaining a passing grade in Buddhism is neither mandatory nor requisite for progression to the General Certificate of Education Advanced Level (G.C.E. A/L) studies. Instruction in Buddhism at the A/L is confined to those students who elect to pursue the subject, which results in a limited enrolment. This trend continues into higher education, where only a small fraction of students opt to specialize in religious studies with a focus on Buddhism.

The marginal prioritization of Buddhism in Sri Lanka's highly competitive examination system, governed by the Ministry of Education, elucidates the lack of motivation among students to engage with Buddhist studies. This phenomenon is compounded by a significant disjunction between the pedagogical materials used to teach Buddhism and the practical application of Buddhist principles. Although Buddhism advocates for a pragmatic approach to alleviating individual suffering, the current educational syllabus fails to convey this effectively to students.

The issue is further exacerbated by the apparent disregard among educational policymakers and curriculum developers for empirical data and research findings pertinent to the pedagogy of Buddhist studies. Despite the critical importance of aligning the curriculum with scientifically analysed educational methodologies, this alignment remains neglected. Moreover, student feedback, which is crucial for the iterative development of a responsive and effective curriculum, is conspicuously absent from the discourse on educational reform in this context.

Research indicates that the efficacy of religious education, particularly in Buddhism, can be significantly enhanced through the integration of contemporary pedagogical strategies and the incorporation of student perspectives (Wijayaratne, 2019; Gamage, 2018). The failure to adopt a research-informed approach in the development of the Buddhist curriculum not only undermines the educational experience but also impedes the potential for students to internalize and apply Buddhist principles in a meaningful manner. Consequently, there exists an urgent need for a systematic review and overhaul of the Buddhist studies curriculum, informed by rigorous academic research and attentive to the lived experiences of students within the educational system.

The teachings of the Buddha reveal a profound endorsement of inquiry and scepticism. Disciples were encouraged to critically evaluate these teachings, to apply them in their daily lives, and to verify their validity through personal experience. Rather than unquestioning faith being demanded, a pragmatic approach designed to produce tangible transformations in one's life was advocated. Consequently, the teachings of the Buddha can be broadly regarded as falsifiable; adherence to the Eight fold Path without achieving the cessation of suffering renders the teachings ineffective for that individual, or suggests flaws in the methods employed in practising the Path.

This principle is epitomized in the Buddha's directive in the Kalama Sutta, where the Kalamas, bewildered by the plethora of spiritual doctrines encountered, were counselled: "Do not go upon what has been acquired by repeated hearing, nor upon tradition, nor upon rumor, nor upon what is in a scripture, nor upon surmise. When you yourselves know: 'These things are bad; these things are blamable; these things are censured by the wise; undertaken and observed, these things lead to harm and ill,' abandon them."(Dipobhasadhamma, 2023).

Sri Lankan students are predominantly introduced to Buddhism as a theoretical subject, with approximately 75% of them passing the General Certificate of Education Ordinary Level (GCE O/L) examination in this discipline. The passing rate of O/L Buddhism was 82.63% in 2022 (Ministry of Education, 2023). However, this academic success does not translate into the practical application of Dhamma in their daily lives, thereby failing to achieve inner peace and mindfulness. Educational theorists and Vipassana practitioners contend that the essence of Buddhist education - experiential understanding through continual Vipassana practice - cannot be effectively condensed into a conventional school syllabus (Hart, 1991).

The Sri Lankan Buddhist education system predominantly emphasizes academic achievements rather than fostering a deep, intrinsic understanding and practice of Buddhist teachings. This study aims to bridge this gap by investigating the effectiveness of the current Buddhism syllabus in promoting the intrinsic achievements of the learning outcomes specified for grade 10.

1.3 PRIOR RESEARCH

Numerous studies and educational critiques have highlighted the disparity between the theoretical instruction of Buddhism in schools and the practical application of its

principles. Dhammasami (2013) underscores that contemporary Buddhist education often produces graduates who are more interested in obtaining formal qualifications than in achieving enlightenment. Kirthisinghe and Amarasuriya (2009) trace the historical evolution of Buddhist education in Sri Lanka, noting a shift towards an exam-centric approach since the establishment of Buddhist Sunday schools by Henry Olcott in the 19th century.

Thongdee et al. (2021) emphasize the critical role of teachers' moral and ethical behavior in preserving cultural values. Massoudi (2010) discusses the use of true recorded stories in Buddhism education to convey moral lessons. Collectively, these studies suggest that while the current curriculum covers Buddhist philosophy, it fails to engage students in a manner that fosters deep, intrinsic understanding and practice.

A syllabus is indispensable for educational institutions, including secondary schools, as it functions as a foundational framework for the realization of learning outcomes. Evaluating the efficacy of the existing Buddhism curriculum in Sri Lankan schools, particularly for grade 10, is paramount to ensuring educational quality, given that grade 11 students participate in the General Certificate of Education Ordinary Level examination. Following this examination, only a marginal number of students opt to pursue Buddhism in their advanced level education. This literature review synthesizes research and perspectives on curriculum effectiveness, student perceptions, variables impacting learning outcomes, and recommendations for curricular enhancement in the context of teaching Buddhism in schools. Nelson and Yang (2021) contend that a comprehensive review of religious education in Northern Ireland in 2007 facilitated the implementation of core syllabuses for various religions, underscoring the necessity for analogous research in other contexts.

This review is structured around four principal themes: alignment of the curriculum with learning outcomes, student perceptions and their impact on learning, factors influencing learning outcomes in Buddhist education, and recommendations for curriculum enhancement.

Concerning curriculum alignment, educational scholars emphasize the imperative of ensuring that the syllabus aligns with the philosophical and ethical objectives of Buddhism. Dhammasami (2013) posits that contemporary Buddhist syllabuses are oriented towards producing graduates who prioritize obtaining qualifications over attaining enlightenment. In the Sri Lankan context, Kirthisinghe and Amarasuriya (2009) observe that the establishment of the first Buddhist Sunday school by Henry Olcott in 1881 shifted the focus of traditional Buddhists from enlightenment to passing examinations, thereby fostering the development of exam-centric syllabuses.

Regarding student perceptions and learning impact, students predominantly engage with Buddhism through textbooks provided by the Ministry of Education, which delineate predefined goals in teachers' guides but not in student textbooks. Teachers are expected to embody moral and ethical standards, maintain positive interpersonal interactions, and preserve cultural traditions and appropriate attitudes (Thongdee et al., 2021). Cultural and socioeconomic factors also significantly influence students' perceptions of Buddhist teachings and their interactions within educational settings, with much of Buddhism being imparted through documented narratives (Massoudi, 2010).

Factors impacting the delivery of Buddhism lessons include the emphasis on self-responsibility and the necessity of an unbiased, impartial mind to comprehend

Buddhist teachings. Klar (2011) advocates for Buddhist children to engage in daily meditation and reflection to internalize these teachings effectively.

Assessing the effectiveness of the current curriculum for teaching Buddhism in Sri Lankan schools is crucial for the achievement of learning outcomes. This literature review integrates both local and international research, examining various facets of curricular effectiveness, student perspectives, influencing factors, and recommendations for development.

1.4 RESEARCH GAP

Despite the acknowledged importance of practical application in Buddhist education, a significant gap persists within the current Sri Lankan school curricula. Existing research has not comprehensively evaluated the effectiveness of the Buddhism syllabus in fostering intrinsic achievements of the learning outcomes specified for the grade 10. Furthermore, there is a dearth of comprehensive studies incorporating feedback from both students and teachers to assess the alignment of the curriculum with its intended goals. In addition, proper evaluations on the Buddhism textbooks are not executed. The validity of those texts is not tested by aligning their content to what the “Tipitaka” states to verify that they do not promote misconceptions through misleading information. Previous studies emphasize the teaching methodologies and methods instead of examining the content and syllabus of Buddhism.

1.5 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The central problem addressed in this research is the potential inadequacy of the current syllabus for teaching Buddhism in Sri Lankan schools in fostering intrinsic achievements of the learning outcomes specified for grade 10. Despite the high pass rates in the GCE O/L examinations conducted prior to the year 2022, students often

fail to apply Buddhist principles in their daily lives to achieve inner peace and mindfulness.

1.6 RESEARCH AIM AND OBJECTIVES

This section reveals the ultimate aim and the objectives which run the research.

1.6.1 Aim

The overarching aim of this research is to investigate the effectiveness of the current syllabus for teaching Buddhism as a subject in Sri Lankan school system in promoting the intrinsic achievements of intended learning outcomes specified in the syllabus of grade 10 that contributes for a considerable part of the curriculum to be covered before the “G.C.E. ordinary Level Examination”.

1.6.2 Objectives

- I. Assess the existing syllabus of grade 10 for teaching Buddhism in Sri Lankan schools as per the intended learning outcomes.
- II. Examine the perceptions of students of grade 10 regarding the impact of Buddhism as a subject on their achievements of learning outcomes.
- III. Identify the factors influencing the intrinsic achievements of learning outcomes within the context of teaching Buddhism through survey, interviewing and analysing documents.
- IV. Propose recommendations for enhancing the effectiveness of teaching Buddhism as a subject to foster intrinsic achievements of learning outcomes.

1.7 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- I. How well does the present curriculum for teaching Buddhism align with the specified learning outcomes for grade 10?

- II. What are the perceptions of grade 10 students regarding the impact of Buddhism as a subject on their achievement of the specified learning outcomes?
- III. What factors affect students' internal mastery of the learning objectives outlined in the Buddhism syllabus for grade 10, in both the teachers' and students perspectives?
- IV. What recommendations can be made to increase the efficacy of teaching Buddhism as a subject to facilitate the actual success of academic outcomes as outlined in the grade 10 Buddhism syllabus?

1.8 KEY TERMS AND ASSUMPTIONS

In the research study, key terms and assumptions are fundamental components that help clarify the scope, context, and foundation of the research.

1.8.1 Key Terms

Key terms are specific words or phrases that are central to the topic of the research.

- I. Intrinsic Achievements: The internalization and practical application of Buddhist teachings that contribute to personal growth and mindfulness.
- II. Vipassana: A form of meditation focusing on the deep understanding of impermanence, suffering, and non-self that guides the practitioner towards the everlasting happiness called "*Nibbana*".
- III. Tipitaka or Thripitaka: The traditional Buddhist scriptures consisting of 57 books, considered the comprehensive guide to the Lord Buddha's teachings.
- IV. Learning Outcomes: The specific objectives and competencies that students are expected to achieve as outlined in the curriculum.

1.8.2 Assumptions

Assumptions are statements that are accepted as true or certain, without proof, for the purposes of the research.

- I. The current curriculum is primarily theoretical and exam-centric, lacking in the practical application of Buddhist teachings.
- II. Students' perceptions and experiences provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of the curriculum.
- III. The recommendations proposed will be based on empirical evidence gathered from only the grade 10 Buddhist students and teachers of Buddhism.
- IV. The grade 10 Buddhism textbook analysis coincides the proposed content changes to allow the students achieve the intended learning outcomes intrinsically.

1.9 METHODOLOGY

This study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative data collection methods to gain a comprehensive understanding of the research problem.

1.9.1 Sampling

Stratified random sampling is utilized to ensure a diverse representation of students from various types of schools (urban, rural, government, private, Semi-government) in the Anuradhapura district. A sample size of 500 students from these educational zones will be included.

1.9.2 Data Collection Methods

Following data collection methods are executed.

- I. Questionnaires: Structured questionnaires will be distributed among students to collect quantifiable information about their perceptions and experiences with the existing Buddhism curriculum.
- II. Interviews: Semi-structured interviews with selected students will provide deeper insights into their experiences and intrinsic achievements. Selected students' verbally expressed insights are recorded to be analysed.
- III. Document Analysis: Analysis of students' Buddhism marks from their report cards to correlate academic performance with intrinsic achievements. Besides, the students' perceptions and insights gained through the survey are analysed against the intended learning outcomes.

1.9.3 Data Analysis

Data gathered are analysed in two aspects as described below.

- I. Quantitative Data Analysis: Descriptive and inferential statistics will be used to summarize the data and identify trends and patterns.
- II. Qualitative Data Analysis: Thematic analysis will be conducted on the interview transcripts to identify emerging themes related to intrinsic development and instructional strategies.

1.10 LIMITATIONS AND DELIMITATIONS

To define the boundaries and constraints of this study, this section has been allocated.

1.10.1 Limitations

Limitations refer to constraints or restrictions that are beyond the control of the researcher and may impact the results or the interpretation of the study. These are inherent weaknesses or constraints that could affect the validity and reliability of the research findings.

- I. The study is limited to schools in the Anuradhapura district, which may not fully represent the diverse educational contexts across Sri Lanka.
- II. The reliance on self-reported data from students may introduce biases.
- III. The study's time frame (five months) may limit the depth of data collection and analysis.

1.10.2 Delimitations

Delimitations refer to the choices made by the researcher that define the boundaries of the study. These are the parameters or scope within which the study is conducted, and they are intentionally set by the researcher to narrow the focus and manage the study's feasibility.

- I. The research focuses solely on the effectiveness of the Buddhism syllabus for grade 10, excluding other grade levels.
- II. The study does not include an in-depth analysis of teacher training programs or other external factors influencing curriculum delivery.

1.11 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE OUTCOMES

The findings of this study bear profound implications:

- I. **Pedagogical Advancement:** Insights into students' perceptions can inform improvements in teaching strategies and pedagogy.
- II. **Curriculum Enhancement:** The study will provide evidence-based recommendations for aligning the Buddhism curriculum more closely with its intended learning outcomes.
- III. **Resource Allocation and Development:** Policymakers can use the findings to allocate resources more effectively for teacher training and professional development.

- IV. Student Support and Assistance: The study's recommendations can guide the establishment of support systems to help students succeed in their studies of Buddhism.
- V. Improved Stakeholder Cooperation: The findings may foster increased collaboration among educators, students, parents, and policymakers.
- VI. Extended Research and Monitoring: The study may highlight areas needing further investigation, prompting ongoing evaluation and improvement of the Buddhism syllabus.

1.12 CHAPTER OUTLINE

- I. Introduction: Overview, background, prior research, research gap, statement of the problem, research aim and objectives, research questions, key terms and assumptions, methodology, limitations and delimitations, significance of the outcomes, chapter outline, and summary.
- II. Literature Review: Detailed analysis of existing literature on the effectiveness of Buddhist education, student perceptions, influencing factors, and recommendations for curriculum enhancement.
- III. Methodology: Comprehensive explanation of the research design, sampling strategy, data collection methods, and data analysis techniques.
- IV. Findings: Presentation and analysis of the research data, including quantitative and qualitative results.
- V. Discussion: Interpretation of the findings in relation to the research questions and objectives, including implications for practice and policy.
- VI. Conclusion: Summary of the research, key findings, contributions to the field, limitations, and suggestions for future research.

1.13 SUMMARY OF CHAPTER ONE

This chapter has meticulously established the foundational framework for the research study entitled "Examining the Impact of the Current Syllabus for Teaching Buddhism on Students' Intrinsic Achievements as Dictated in the Syllabi of Grade 10". The comprehensive introduction systematically delineates the research background, accentuates relevant prior studies, identifies a significant research lacuna, and articulates the problem statement. Furthermore, it elaborates on the research aim and objectives, formulates the research questions, and delineates key terms and assumptions. The methodology, encompassing a mixed-methods approach with stratified random sampling, data collection via questionnaires, interviews, and document analysis, and both quantitative and qualitative data analysis, is expounded in detail. The limitations and delimitations of the study are carefully outlined, emphasizing its focus on the Anuradhapura district and the theoretical constraints of the curriculum. The significance of the study's outcomes is discussed, highlighting potential contributions to pedagogical advancement, curriculum enhancement, resource allocation, student support, stakeholder cooperation, and extended research. The chapter concludes with an outline of the subsequent chapters, providing a clear and structured roadmap for the research. This extensive overview establishes the necessity, scope, and potential implications of the study within the context of the Sri Lankan education system, thereby laying a robust groundwork for the ensuing chapters.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION TO RESEARCH LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter reveals two sections- theoretical framework and literature review. The previous endeavours to address the same or mostly relevant issues are studied first and thereby the way of conducting the research is further planned and focused in a unique manner which is enriched with necessary actions to be taken to come up with more accurate and reliable data gathered to be analysed to discover hidden factors which affect the revolution of education through spanning the knowledge and understanding of the effectiveness of the syllabus of Buddhism on the intrinsic achievements expected to be grown in student's mind. The theoretical and conceptual frameworks utilized in the previous research, are also studied and they are reported herein. The backward design framework is selected from all those studied frameworks due to some of its positive features. The priority goes to present the reasons for using the backward design framework while briefing the other frameworks utilized in the other research.

2.2 THEORETICAL AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORKS

Since the grade 10 Buddhism syllabus of local schools focuses on developing students' critical thinking ability, the subject content has been designed to empower the student to take decisions by analysing evidence taking from various trust-worthy sources. Therefore, the learners should be able to assess even the reliability and accuracy of data sources.

2.2.1 Research Based Learning Framework

Mr. Montha Chumsukon and Mr. Niraj Ruangsan's research intends to investigate the pre-service teachers' critical thinking skills using "Research-based Learning" and

“Community Learning Resources”, as well as their satisfaction with learning activities (Chumsukon & Ruangsak, 2021). Chumsukon & Ruangsak claim that a conceptual framework based on research based learning mixed up with community learning resources had provided guidance to execute their study with the implementation of one-shot case study which showed the analytical thinking skills of pre-service teachers. The research paper expresses how several publications demonstrated five stages for integrating "research-based learning" into learning activities: defining the issue that exists, planning the learning activity, implementing learning activities, collecting data, and analysing data to report study findings.

Figure 1: A conceptual framework

The present school Buddhism curriculum in Sri Lanka appears to fall short of the targeted learning goals, which define pupils' intrinsic comprehension and application of the Buddha's teachings. To examine this topic, academics consider adopting the following theoretical frameworks.

2.2.2 Transformative Learning Theory Framework

This theory examines how people critically reflect on their assumptions and beliefs, resulting in a shift in their perspectives and behaviours. It is used to assess if the existing curriculum encourages pupils to critically examine their own views and values in light of Buddhist teachings.

The article "Transformative Experience in Buddhism: A Case Study" is by Chancey (Chancey et al., 2019) meticulously explores the phenomenon of transformational learning among Buddhist monks through the practice of metta, or loving-kindness meditation. The research elucidates that this particular meditative discipline engenders profound transformational experiences, which significantly enhance quotidian existence by expanding consciousness and engendering substantive experiential value. Drawing from the teachings of the Buddha, it is arguable that a monk's complete practice necessitates transformative experiences. It (Pugh, 2011) characterizes these transformative experiences as learning that transcends ordinary boundaries, expanding one's perception and enriching everyday encounters. Rooted in the educational psychology framework, inspired by the work of pragmatist John Dewey (Chancey et al., 2019), their study endeavours to delve into the life orientation and wisdom of Buddhist monks. By examining transformative experiences beyond the confines of formal classroom settings, they seek to push the boundaries of existing research. Additionally, they explore the practical implications of these transformative experiences, applicable across diverse educational contexts.

Figure 2: Transformative Experience

The “Figure 2” illustrates the three components of transformative learning theory and their interactions as per the concepts used in the research framework executed in the aforementioned research.

The initial component, termed motivated usage, occurs when a learner deliberately incorporates acquired knowledge into their quotidian activities. An illustrative instance of motivated usage is observed when a student, having comprehended the principles of gravity in a physics classroom, actively applies this understanding while observing a basketball game. This student, captivated by the principles of gravity, may initiate a discourse with a parent or sibling during the game. The student is then able to elucidate, for instance, the reasons behind certain players' ability to achieve greater vertical leaps than others.

The second facet of transformative education is perceptual expansion, which transpires when a learner integrates novel ideas and concepts, thereby reconfiguring their world-view. For instance, subsequent to acquiring knowledge about the principles of gravity, a student observing a basketball game becomes acutely aware of gravitational forces each time a player executes a jump to perform a dunk or obstruct

a shot. Consequently, the student perceives basketball not merely as an assemblage of players in motion but as an intricate interplay of numerous physical principles, including gravity, inertia, and kinematics, thus bridging theoretical physics and practical observation.

The third constituent, experiential value, materializes when learning transcends mere utility and attains significance for the learner. In the previously mentioned example, the student may develop an enhanced appreciation for the concept of gravity, as it transforms their perception of basketball. No longer observing the players' movements as arbitrary, the student gains insight into the differential abilities of players to jump, grounded in the principles of gravity. This newfound understanding not only augments the student's cognitive framework but also facilitates intellectually enriching discourse with peers or family members, thereby imbuing the learning process with additional social value.

By that time, although the transformative learning theory framework had not been utilized in conducting research in the subjects closely and widely related to ethics and morality, the researchers could use it with their intended purpose related to non-classroom education in the monasteries. Chancey, Hong and Heddy also tries to investigate the matter of concern that the practicality of application of Buddhism in daily routine of disciples. However, as the transformative framework is not mainly used in research closer to ethics and morality, it seems that it has some difficulties in using it in such scenarios. It is more suitable for doing research in subjects like science and technology as it does not highly concern the student's emotional quotient.

2.2.3 Experiential Learning Theory Framework

This method emphasises the value of hands-on, practical experiences in the educational process. Researchers should look into whether the curriculum gives students enough opportunity to engage in Buddhist practices and implement the teachings in their daily lives.

As the limited time spent in school does not permit the students practice and experience the applicability of theories delivered in Buddhism in their day today life career, this theory based framework is not selected in this research. For instance, the eight fold path is to be practised to fully understand the concepts delivered in classroom discussions. All the eight components of the path are practised simultaneously when practice of Vipassana meditation takes place. Therefore, this is skipped in utilization in this research. Although this framework is pragmatic in delivery of lessons, it is not that much appropriate in assessing the effectiveness of syllabus of Buddhism against the intended learning outcomes.

Figure 3: Model of Experiential Learning Theory

The “Figure 3” shows the model of experiential learning theory along with the process and sequence of experiential learning including its concepts, constructs, and

proposition. These components are briefly explained. The foundational tenets of the theory encompass four fundamental elements: experiential engagement, reflective contemplation, cognitive processing, and purposeful enactment. These principles constitute the core stages within the “Experiential Learning Theory” (ELT), commencing with learners encountering novel situations. Upon engaging in authentic experiences, learners engage in reflective introspection, critically assessing the encounter in light of their existing knowledge. Subsequently, they ascend to a higher cognitive plane, contemplating how to assimilate the experience into their mental framework. This reflective synthesis culminates in the translation of abstract insights into tangible actions - a transformative process that both solidifies learning constructs and engenders fresh experiential cycles. Iteratively, learners revisit this dynamic cycle, refining their understanding and skill acquisition.

2.2.4 Constructivist Learning Theory

This theory suggests that learners actively construct their own understanding by connecting new information to their prior knowledge and experiences. Researchers could investigate whether the curriculum encourages students to actively engage with and make meaning of the Buddhist teachings.

When used as a research framework, the constructivist theory focuses need of understanding the learner's perspective, as well as the social and environmental elements that influence their knowledge production. Qualitative approaches such as interviews, observations, and document analysis are ideally suited for investigating these issues. The purpose is to build comprehensive, grounded understandings of the learning process rather than to verify preconceived ideas.

Using a constructivist theoretical framework to assess the efficacy of teaching Buddhism in Sri Lankan schools has a few possible drawbacks:

I. Subjectivity and Bias: Constructivism emphasizes learners' subjective experiences and perceptions, potentially introducing bias. Individual interpretations vary significantly, complicating the generalization of findings and the construction of objective efficacy metrics.

II. Assessing Outcomes: Constructivist approaches prioritize qualitative data, emphasizing personal reflections and narratives over quantitative metrics. However, this emphasis on subjective insights complicates evaluation, rendering it challenging to systematically and reliably measure the impact of Buddhist teachings on students' understanding and behavior. When assessing the effectiveness of teaching Buddhism in local syllabus driven schools in Sri Lanka, it would not be more suitable due to this inapplicability.

III. Constructivist learning theory is basically appropriate in a classroom where most of the students have a high level of intelligent quotient. However, in Sri Lankan local syllabus driven schools, it occurs very rarely. “The Research and Development - School Examination Branch of Department of Examinations - Sri Lanka” announces that 84329 students (26.64%) and 39601 students (17.37%) have failed the subjects Mathematics and Buddhism respectively at the G.C.E. O/L examination in 2022, (ministry, 2023). As the figures shown there, to utilize the constructivist learning theory framework is better to set in classes greatly intelligent students.

IV. Contextual Variability: According to the constructivist theory, learning is highly contextualised and impacted by the unique environment and interactions. In Sri Lanka's complex socio-cultural landscape, differing settings among schools may

result in variable implementation and outcomes, making it difficult to make broad conclusions regarding the efficiency of Buddhist education.

V. Assessment Complexity: Traditional assessment techniques, like conventional testing, may not be compatible with constructivist concepts. Creating adequate evaluation instruments that effectively reflect the depth and breadth of students' learning experiences and integration of Buddhist teachings is difficult and time-consuming.

2.3 BACKWARD DESIGN FRAMEWORK

The "Backward Design Framework" constitutes a sophisticated pedagogical methodology wherein curriculum development is initiated with a clear articulation of the desired educational outcomes. This model entails a reverse-engineering process, meticulously aligning instructional strategies and assessments with the predefined objectives to ensure that students achieve the intended competencies. Its applicability is particularly salient in the context of evaluating and enhancing educational programs. By employing this framework, educators can ensure that students not only succeed in examinations but also deeply assimilate and pragmatically apply Buddhist principles in their daily lives. This technique is used to assess the existing curriculum's conformity with the targeted learning goals for students' intrinsic grasp and application of Buddhist concepts.

The following section presents how the "Backward Design Framework" is utilized to conduct the research on the effectiveness of the Buddhism curriculum in fostering students' intrinsic achievements of learning outcomes.

I. Identify Desired Results

It begins with explicit description of the desired learning outcomes, which reflect the inherent knowledge and application of Buddhist concepts that students should accomplish. These go beyond just factual knowledge and emphasise deeper interaction with the lessons intrinsic learning outcomes represent a profound integration of Buddhist teachings, encompassing moral discipline (Seela), concentration (Samadhi), and wisdom (Panna). These outcomes extend beyond mere theoretical understanding, emphasizing practical application. By cultivating these qualities, students not only gain intellectual insights but also embark on a transformative journey toward the cessation of suffering and the ultimate realization of “*Nibbana*”.

II. Determine Acceptable Evidence

It creates exams that directly measure students' abilities to exhibit the intended educational outcomes. This might include introspective essays, talks, or projects in which students must apply Buddhist teachings to their own lives and experiences.

III. Plan Learning Activities

Structure the curriculum and classroom activities to actively engage students in exploring the Buddhist teachings and their relevance to their personal growth and development. Provide opportunities for experiential learning, critical reflection, and practical application of the principles.

Starting with the desired intrinsic learning outcomes and aligning assessments and instructional activities accordingly, the backward design framework can help ensure that the Buddhism curriculum effectively fosters students' deeper understanding and

internalisation of the Buddha's teachings. This strategy changes the focus away from just covering knowledge and towards fostering transformational learning experiences. Using the "Backward Design Framework," the study assesses the grade 10 Buddhism curriculum's efficacy in generating intrinsic successes. This strategy guarantees that the curriculum not only prepares students for examinations, but also fosters a deep, meaningful understanding and practical application of Buddhist teachings, eventually directing students to the desired learning goals.

2.4 PREVIOUS RESEARCH

Numerous studies and critiques have found a discrepancy between how Buddhism is taught in schools and how students use its precepts in their daily lives. Dhammasami (2013) notes that current Buddhist education frequently creates graduates who are more concerned with obtaining degrees than with reaching enlightenment. Kirthisinghe and Amarasuriya (2009) describe how Henry Olcott established Buddhist Sunday schools in the nineteenth century, shifting the emphasis from spiritual growth to exam preparation.

These results reveal that, while the existing curriculum contains Buddhist philosophy, it does not engage students in a way that promotes deep, personal comprehension and application of the teachings.

It is critical to assess the effectiveness of the present Buddhism curriculum in Sri Lankan schools, particularly among grade 10 pupils. This is because grade 11 students take the General Certificate of Education Ordinary Level test, and only a tiny proportion opt to continue their studies in Buddhism.

This review looks upon four major themes:

- I. How closely the curriculum matches with the desired learning goals.

II. How pupils' perspectives influence their learning.

III. Factors influencing learning outcomes in Buddhist education.

IV. Curriculum improvement recommendations.

On curricular alignment, researchers emphasise the need of ensuring that the syllabus aligns with Buddhism's philosophical and ethical aims. Dhammasami (2013) contends that current Buddhist curricula are more concerned with developing graduates who value degrees above enlightenment.

According to student perspectives, pupils study Buddhism mostly from textbooks given by the education government. These textbooks set goals for teachers but not for students. Teachers are supposed to demonstrate moral and ethical behaviour while also preserving cultural traditions (Thongdee et al., 2021). Culture and socioeconomic status also influence how students perceive and respond to Buddhist teachings (Massoudi, 2010).

Other variables that influence learning include the emphasis on self-responsibility and the requirement for an unbiased attitude in order to appreciate Buddhist ideas. Klar (2011) suggests that Buddhist students use daily meditation and introspection to internalise the teachings.

Finally, the study concludes that while the existing Buddhism curriculum in Sri Lankan schools covers intellectual material, it fails to properly nurture students' profound, practical knowledge and application of the teachings. Addressing this gap requires curriculum change, teacher training, and an emphasis on learning objectives and assessment to improve the efficacy of teaching the subject Buddhism in school.

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION TO RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research embarks on a comprehensive exploration of the Buddhism curriculum in Sri Lankan schools, specifically focusing on its efficacy in facilitating the attainment of learning objectives for Grade 10 students. This investigation aligns with the domain of educational research, with a particular emphasis on curriculum evaluation, content validation and educational effectiveness.

3.2 APPLICATION OF BACKWARD DESIGN FRAMEWORK IN THE RESEARCH

The employment of the “Backward Design Framework” underscores pragmatic orientation of this research, ensuring methodological alignment with contemporary educational praxis. This pedagogical paradigm, delineated into three sequential stages - identification of desired results, determination of acceptable evidence, and planning of learning experiences which prioritize outcomes that are not merely quantifiable but also pragmatically implementable.

Stage 1: Identifying Desired Results

The initial phase of the “Backward Design Framework” necessitates a comprehensive elucidation of the Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs) prescribed by the Grade 10 Buddhism syllabus. These ILOs prioritize the cultivation of intrinsic development, encompassing empathy, mindfulness, ethical decision-making, and a nuanced comprehension of Buddhist teachings that transcends rote memorization. Nevertheless, empirical observations derived from current syllabus implementation expose a discernible disparity between these aspirational goals and the actual behavioural manifestations of students.

A practical example is elaborated herein. A concrete instantiation of a desired result might entail students internalizing "The Four Noble Truths" and substantiating this understanding through the resolution of interpersonal conflicts in their daily routines. For instance, a student who has attained a profound comprehension of the concept of avoiding harm may actively abstain from bullying behaviours within the school environment.

To operationalize these desired results, it is imperative to translate abstract outcomes into observable and measurable behaviours. For example, students should exhibit patience during collaborative activities, refrain from harsh speech, and make environmentally conscious decisions that align with the Buddhist principle of non-harming ("*Ahimsa*").

Stage 2: Determining Acceptable Evidence

The second stage of the backward design framework, "Determining Acceptable Evidence", plays a pivotal role in assessing whether students have achieved the desired intrinsic development as outlined in the intended learning outcomes of the Buddhism syllabus. This stage utilizes a mixed-methods approach, integrating various data collection methods to ensure a comprehensive and multidimensional evaluation of students' outcomes.

To achieve this, the study employs triangulation of evidence, drawing upon multiple sources to validate findings. First, test scores from Buddhism term test results provide insights into students' theoretical understanding of the subject matters. High scores indicate a mastery of Buddhist concepts and principles at a cognitive level. Second, questionnaire responses are designed to assess the practical application of these principles in real-life contexts, exploring how students respond to challenges or

interact with peers, reflecting the internalization of Buddhist teachings. Third, interview data offers deeper qualitative insights, where students elaborate on their implementation of concepts such as “The Eightfold Path”. For instance, they might describe how they practice “Right Speech” by avoiding gossip or maintain “Right Concentration” during academic tasks. Finally, teacher feedback provides an external perspective on observable behavioural changes in students, such as enhanced cooperation, self-discipline, or empathy.

A further method of gathering evidence involves situational judgments during interviews. In this approach, students are presented with hypothetical scenarios, such as witnessing a peer being teased. Their responses- whether they choose to intervene or remain passive - are analysed to evaluate their intrinsic development. Such scenarios are specifically designed to reflect key Buddhist values, including compassion and moral courage. This comprehensive and diverse approach ensures that the evidence collected provides a robust foundation for assessing both the theoretical understanding and behavioural application of the syllabus.

Stage 3: Planning Learning Experiences And Instruction: Forging The Link Between Theory And Praxis

The culminating stage of the “Backward Design Framework” prioritizes the reconceptualization of the curriculum to bridge the chasm between theoretical content and its practical application. This phase is dedicated to the transformation of passive learning into active engagement, ensuring that students not only attain academic excellence but also internalize positive behavioural modifications rooted in Buddhist teachings. The overarching objective is to cultivate a holistic learning experience that seamlessly integrates cognitive understanding with practical application, fostering

moral and ethical growth in tandem with academic achievement. In the following discourse, the incorporation of scenario-based learning, reflective practices, teacher-facilitated discussions, and community engagement projects is explicated as efficacious strategies according to the view of Buddhism teachers who participated in the interviews conducted during the data collection phase of this research.

Scenario-based Learning: Bridging Theory And Behavioural Application

Scenario-based learning represents an instructional methodology that strategically employs hypothetical or authentic real-world situations to prompt students to apply Buddhist principles in a meaningful context. This pedagogical approach is designed to cultivate critical thinking, emotional self-regulation, and informed decision-making, which are pivotal for transitioning from theoretical understanding to observable behavioural transformation.

A representative example involves a student experiencing emotional distress after losing a competition. In this context, the educator facilitates reflective engagement with the Buddhist principle of impermanence (*Anichcha*), guiding the student to recognize the transient nature of both triumphs and setbacks. This reflective process enables the student to manage disappointment constructively, fostering emotional resilience and psychological stability.

The pedagogical significance of scenario-based learning lies in its ability to embed abstract Buddhist teachings into scenarios that resonate with students' lived experiences. By anchoring principles within relatable frameworks, learners are empowered to internalize these concepts and integrate them autonomously into their daily actions. This experiential learning model effectively transitions passive acquisition of knowledge into proactive and transformative behavioural change,

thereby reinforcing the practical relevance and enduring impact of Buddhist education.

Reflective Practices: Fostering Metacognition and Ethical Development

Reflective practices represent a pedagogical approach designed to facilitate introspection and the integration of theoretical knowledge into students' personal and social contexts. Through structured activities such as journal writing, students are encouraged to examine their actions, decisions, and thought processes in light of Buddhist principles that have to be individually experienced as a meditator. This method cultivates metacognition, enhancing self-awareness and promoting a continuous trajectory of moral and ethical development.

For instance, a reflective journal might document a student's conscious efforts to embody Right Livelihood, such as abstaining from harmful actions like gossip or deceit, or their application of mindfulness to manage stress during high-pressure situations such as examinations. This introspective exercise not only reinforces the practical relevance of Buddhist teachings but also encourages students to develop strategies for aligning their behaviours with these principles in diverse contexts. Teachers normally do not train the students to practice *Samatha* or *Vipassana* meditation under a proper formal guidance.

The pedagogical impact of reflective practices extends beyond individual development. By critically analysing their experiences, students deepen their understanding of the interconnection between abstract Buddhist ideals and real-world applications. Furthermore, the insights gained from these journals offer educators a nuanced understanding of each student's moral and ethical growth. This feedback enables educators to provide personalized support, addressing specific areas for

improvement while reinforcing positive behaviours. Through this iterative process, reflective practices become a powerful tool for bridging theoretical learning with sustained personal transformation.

Teacher-Led Discussions: A Catalyst for Ethical Reasoning and Collaborative Learning

Teacher-led discussions constitute a dynamic pedagogical approach that fosters collaborative learning and ethical reasoning by encouraging students to articulate and share their interpretations and lived experiences of Buddhist teachings. This strategy not only reinforces theoretical concepts but also facilitates their contextualization within real-world scenarios, thereby promoting a deeper and more nuanced understanding.

For example, following a lesson on *Karuna* (compassion), students may recount personal anecdotes in which they provided assistance to a friend or peer in need. Such narratives enable participants to explore the practical application of Buddhist principles, bridging the gap between abstract ethical concepts and tangible actions. These exchanges serve as a means of embedding Buddhist teachings within students' social interactions, emphasizing the transformative potential of compassion as a guiding value.

The pedagogical impact of teacher-led discussions is multifaceted. By engaging in these structured dialogues, students develop essential interpersonal competencies, including active listening, empathy, and mutual respect—key attributes for moral and ethical development. Furthermore, the collaborative nature of such discussions promotes the co-construction of knowledge, enabling learners to benefit from diverse perspectives and interpretations. Teachers, in their role as facilitators, steer

conversations to ensure depth and relevance while fostering an inclusive and supportive environment that encourages open expression. Ultimately, this methodology cultivates a community of learners who collectively internalize and reinforce the practical significance of Buddhist ethical teachings in both academic and personal spheres.

Community Engagement Projects: A Bridge Between Theory and Practice

Community engagement projects offer a dynamic pedagogical approach that extends the learning environment beyond the confines of the classroom, enabling students to apply Buddhist principles within a broader societal context. This strategy fosters a sense of responsibility, civic engagement, and a practical understanding of ethical conduct.

For instance, students might organize a community clean-up initiative, aligning their actions with the Buddhist principle of environmental stewardship and respect for nature. Through such activities, students experience first-hand the collective impact of altruistic actions and the fulfilment derived from contributing to societal well-being.

The pedagogical impact of community engagement projects is multifaceted. These initiatives instil a sense of agency and purpose in students, demonstrating how Buddhist teachings can drive meaningful societal change. Additionally, community engagement nurtures essential skills such as teamwork, leadership, and empathy, reinforcing the applicability of ethical principles in diverse contexts. By bridging the gap between theory and practice, these projects empower students to become active agents of positive change within their communities.

Through these methodologies, the curriculum evolves into a dynamic framework that prioritizes both intellectual mastery and moral transformation accordingly the

teachers' perspectives on the teaching methodologies utilized in delivery of lessons in Buddhism syllabus. By integrating scenario-based learning, reflective practices, teacher-led discussions, and community projects, students are guided toward a holistic understanding of Buddhist teachings that transcends rote learning, enabling them to embody these principles in their personal and social lives. This approach ensures that education serves as a transformative force, cultivating individuals who are both ethically grounded and academically proficient. However, it happens in school in various ways. Although the methodologies are applied in school, their foundation seems missing. That is nothing but the practice of Vipassana meditation which is the unique method of getting liberated, as per the Lord Buddha's words.

3.2 ALIGNING BLOOM'S TAXONOMY WITH BACKWARD DESIGN FRAMEWORK

To apply "Bloom's Taxonomy" in the context of this research scenario using the "Backward Design Framework", the research can be approached with a focus on aligning the learning outcomes and assessment methods to support intrinsic development in students. Here is how to break it down in relation to the research objectives and questions.

3.2.1 Backward Design Stage 1: Clarifying The Desired Results

Research Objective I: Assessing The Cognitive Depth Of The Grade 10 Buddhism Syllabus

This research objective aims to critically evaluate the Grade 10 Buddhism syllabus through the lens of Bloom's Taxonomy. By examining the specified learning outcomes, the study will determine the extent to which the syllabus promotes higher-order thinking skills beyond mere factual recall. The investigation will assess whether

the syllabus encourages students to engage in application, analysis, synthesis, and evaluation- skills that are essential for fostering intrinsic development.

For instance, the study will examine whether the syllabus requires students to critically analyse the applicability of Buddhist teachings to their own lives. Does it encourage self-reflection and ethical reasoning, thereby prompting behavioural change? By addressing these questions, the research seeks to identify potential gaps in the syllabus and opportunities for enhancement.

Research Objective II: Examining Students' Perceptions Of Buddhist Education

The second research objective focuses on understanding students' perceptions of the impact of Buddhism on their cognitive and behavioural development. To achieve this, the study will employ Bloom's Taxonomy to frame interview or questionnaire questions that assess students' comprehension and application of the material.

For example, questions such as "Can you explain what aspects of Buddhism influence your thoughts or behaviour?" will assess students' comprehension of Buddhist concepts. Similarly, questions such as "Can you give an example of how you have used Buddhist teachings in your daily life?" will evaluate students' ability to apply these teachings to real-world situations. By analysing students' responses, the research will shed light on the extent to which Buddhist education leads to meaningful cognitive and behavioural change, or whether it remains superficial, limited to rote memorization of facts.

3.2.2 Backward Design Stage 2: Determining Acceptable Evidence

This is a deep dive into students' learning.

Research Objective III: Identifying Factors Influencing Intrinsic Learning Outcomes

This research objective aims to delve into the depth of students' learning by employing Bloom's Taxonomy. By analysing student performance data and questionnaire responses, the study will assess whether students are achieving higher-order thinking skills beyond mere knowledge recall and understanding. The focus will be on analysing students' ability to break down Buddhist teachings and examine their impact on life choices (analysis), synthesize Buddhist principles with personal experiences and lifestyles (synthesis), and evaluate the relevance of Buddhist practices to their own well-being and mindset (evaluation). By identifying patterns in student performance, the study will shed light on the factors that influence intrinsic learning and the extent to which the current curriculum and pedagogical approaches are effective in fostering such development.

Research Objective IV: Proposing Recommendations For Enhancing Effectiveness

Based on the findings of the previous research objectives, this final objective aims to propose specific recommendations for enhancing the effectiveness of the Grade 10 Buddhism curriculum. By analysing the extent to which students are demonstrating higher-order cognitive skills, the study will identify areas where the syllabus can be revised to promote deeper learning.

For instance, the study may recommend incorporating activities that encourage the application of Buddhist principles to real-world contexts, such as case studies and problem-based learning. Additionally, the study may suggest the use of reflective journals and discussion groups to foster critical thinking, self-reflection, and the synthesis of knowledge.

Furthermore, the study may propose revisions to assessment practices to move beyond traditional exams, which often prioritize factual recall and understanding. Instead, the study may advocate for alternative assessment methods, such as self-assessment, peer assessment, and performance-based assessments that require students to apply their knowledge and skills to real-world problems and ethical dilemmas. By implementing these recommendations, the study aims to contribute to the development of a more effective and engaging Buddhist education curriculum.

3.2.3 Backward Design Stage 3: Planning The Learning Experience: A Blueprint For Transformative Learning

The third stage of Backward Design involves the meticulous planning of learning experiences that are designed to foster active learning and promote the internalization of Buddhist teachings. By integrating Bloom's Taxonomy, educators can ensure that students move beyond rote memorization and engage in higher-order thinking skills.

The learning journey should commence with the introduction of foundational knowledge of Buddhist concepts (remembering). Subsequently, students should be engaged in group discussions or reflective exercises to explain how Buddhism relates to their lives (understanding). To encourage the application of Buddhist teachings, students should be presented with opportunities to apply these principles to their daily decisions and challenges (applying).

To foster critical thinking and analysis, students should be encouraged to compare Buddhist principles with other ethical frameworks or life philosophies (analysing). By engaging in self-reflection and evaluation, students can assess the personal impact of their learning and identify areas for improvement (evaluating). Finally, to cultivate creativity and innovation, students should be invited to propose ways to incorporate

Buddhist values into their communities or create projects that reflect their understanding of Buddhist teachings (creating). By implementing a comprehensive approach that incorporates all levels of Bloom's Taxonomy, educators can empower students to become active learners and ethical practitioners.

3.2.4 Integrating Bloom's Taxonomy Into The Backward Design Framework

Bloom's Taxonomy provides a robust framework for assessing the cognitive depth of learning outcomes and instructional practices. By aligning research questions with the various levels of Bloom's Taxonomy, this study aims to comprehensively evaluate the effectiveness of the Grade 10 Buddhism curriculum in fostering intrinsic development.

Research Question I: Aligning Curriculum With Learning Outcomes

This research question seeks to determine the extent to which the current Buddhism curriculum aligns with the specified learning outcomes for Grade 10. By mapping the syllabus to Bloom's Taxonomy, the study will assess whether the curriculum extends beyond mere recall and understanding to include activities that promote higher-order thinking skills such as application, analysis, synthesis, and evaluation.

Research Question II: Exploring Student Perceptions Of Buddhist Education

This research question aims to investigate students' perceptions of the impact of Buddhism on their academic achievement. By employing a perception survey structured around Bloom's Taxonomy, the study will assess whether students perceive the subject as fostering critical thinking and application of Buddhist teachings, or whether it is primarily focused on memorization and rote learning.

Research Question III: Identifying Factors Influencing Intrinsic Learning

This research question seeks to identify the factors that influence students' internalization of Buddhist teachings. By examining the relationship between teaching methods, student attitudes, and assessment types with different levels of Bloom's Taxonomy, the study will determine the extent to which these factors contribute to the development of higher-order thinking skills.

Research Question IV: Proposing Recommendations For Enhancing Effectiveness

Based on the findings of the previous research questions, this final research question aims to propose specific recommendations for enhancing the effectiveness of the Grade 10 Buddhism curriculum. By aligning the curriculum with all six levels of Bloom's Taxonomy, the study will advocate for instructional practices that promote both cognitive and intrinsic growth.

In conclusion, by employing Bloom's Taxonomy as a component set onto the Backward Design Conceptual Framework, this research will provide valuable insights into the strengths and weaknesses of the current Grade 10 Buddhism curriculum. The findings of this study will inform evidence-based recommendations for improving the curriculum to foster deeper learning and promote the holistic development of students.

3.3 RESEARCH CONTEXT

The present study examines the degree to which Grade 10 students studying Buddhism as a core subject within the Sri Lankan school curriculum have achieved intrinsic behavioural development, as outlined in the intended learning outcomes (ILOs) of the subject syllabus. The research is predicated on the premise that while students demonstrate academic success in terms of marks obtained in term tests and

other examinations, they often fail to exhibit corresponding intrinsic growth in behaviour, attitudes, and values - elements that are central to the pedagogical objectives of teaching Buddhism. This research seeks to evaluate the existing syllabus and propose constructive amendments to ensure alignment between intended learning outcomes and actual student development.

To establish the validity of this premise, the study employs a mixed-methods approach, encompassing questionnaires, interviews, and document analysis. A purposive sampling technique was utilized to identify specific ILOs that emphasize intrinsic development in students. These ILOs were selected by referencing the Teachers' Guide accompanying the Grade 10 Buddhism curriculum. The selected outcomes served as benchmarks to assess whether the recommended textbook content and the teaching-learning process successfully contribute to the cultivation of the desired behavioural and attitudinal changes.

The research is conducted across two schools located within the same geographical region. The first is a semi-government institution attended primarily by students from affluent families with higher socio-economic standing and educated parents. The second is a government school predominantly serving students from economically disadvantaged backgrounds and lower social strata, whose parents typically have limited educational attainment. From these schools, a total sample of 110 Grade 10 students was randomly selected, comprising 51 students from the semi-government school and 59 students from the government school. This random sampling technique, irrespective of the students' academic performance, gender, or other demographic factors, ensured a diverse and representative sample for the research.

The questionnaire was administered in Sinhala, the medium of instruction for the subject, to facilitate accessibility and comprehension. It consisted of 20 questions: 13 true/false items and 7 structured true/false questions requiring participants to provide justifications for their responses. The justifications were essential to validate the accuracy and intentionality of the students' answers. The printed questionnaire was distributed to students during a 40-minute classroom session under the researcher's supervision. To ensure anonymity and minimize response bias, students did not include their names on the answer sheets. Instead, their responses were matched to numbered seating arrangements, which were linked to a separate list maintained confidentially by the researcher.

To corroborate the data collected through the questionnaire, 20% of the sample was selected for follow-up interviews. These interviews were conducted with students who had scored varying marks in the most recent term test. The interviews provided deeper insights into the students' reasoning and enabled cross-validation of their questionnaire responses. Additionally, structured interviews were conducted with five teachers responsible for delivering the Buddhism curriculum to the sampled students. The teacher interviews were designed to assess their pedagogical knowledge, attitudes, and skills, as well as their perceptions of the students' progress toward achieving the ILOs.

Document analysis was another critical component of the research methodology. Certified school attendance records were reviewed to verify the regularity of students' participation in Buddhism lessons. This analysis aimed to explore whether consistent attendance correlated with the achievement of ILOs, particularly those linked to intrinsic behavioural development. Furthermore, students' term test marks for

Buddhism were obtained and analysed to investigate the relationship between academic performance and intrinsic growth. The numerical values derived from the questionnaire and interview responses were compared against the test scores to assess the alignment between students' knowledge acquisition and behavioural transformation.

The research draws on the theoretical framework of the Backward Design Framework to examine the alignment between curriculum content, instructional strategies, and assessment practices. This framework, widely recognized in educational research, emphasizes the importance of identifying desired learning outcomes, designing assessments to measure these outcomes, and planning instructional strategies accordingly. By applying this framework, the study seeks to determine whether the Grade 10 Buddhism syllabus, as currently structured, adequately supports the intrinsic development of students or requires amendments to better fulfil its pedagogical goals. Statistical analysis was performed using "PSPP", an open-source statistical software, to generate descriptive statistics and identify patterns within the data. The analysis facilitated a nuanced understanding of the extent to which the curriculum and pedagogy of the Grade 10 Buddhism syllabus align with the intended outcomes of fostering intrinsic behavioural development.

Through this multi-faceted approach, the research aims to provide an evidence-based evaluation of the Buddhism curriculum. By demonstrating gaps between academic achievement and intrinsic development, the study will inform recommendations for curriculum revision to ensure that the teaching of Buddhism not only imparts knowledge but also engenders the values and behaviours central to the subject's philosophical and educational objectives.

3.4 RESEARCH DESIGN

The study employs a multifaceted approach, incorporating elements of curriculum evaluation research, mixed-methods research, descriptive and exploratory research, and educational policy and practice-based research. The research philosophy applicable behind this effort was “Pragmatism” which is a combination of positivism and interpretivism. For driving the research in quantitative approach, it pictured the quantifiable measures through which the case was objectively taken into consideration under the view of positivism. Due to the qualitative approach followed in the research, it fell into the category of interpretivism driven research with the fact that the reality is subjective. Pragmatism, as a philosophical underpinning for research, prioritizes the pragmatic application of research findings and the selection of methodologies most conducive to addressing the specific research problem. Transcending the traditional dichotomy between interpretivism, which emphasizes subjective understanding and contextual nuance, and positivism, which prioritizes objective, quantifiable phenomena, pragmatism advocates for a problem-centred approach that integrates diverse perspectives. Within the context of this study, pragmatism provides a particularly suitable philosophical framework, given its emphasis on addressing real-world challenges. Specifically, it aligns with the research objective of investigating the disjuncture between academic achievement and intrinsic behavioural development among Grade 10 students studying Buddhism.

3.4.1 Research Philosophy: Pragmatism

This research eschews the dichotomous paradigms of interpretivism and positivism, aiming instead to bridge the gap between theoretical understanding and practical application. The primary objective is to evaluate the extent to which the Grade 10

Buddhism syllabus effectively facilitates the attainment of its intended learning outcomes (ILOs) and to propose evidence-based modifications that can enhance the development of intrinsic behavioural change among students. By adopting a pragmatic approach, the research recognizes the complex and multifaceted nature of the research question and employs a mixed-methods design to generate both qualitative and quantitative data. This methodological pluralism enables a comprehensive understanding of the problem and the formulation of actionable recommendations that can be directly implemented to improve the curriculum and pedagogical practices.

3.4.2 Research Approach: Both Deductive and Inductive Approach

The research started with the observation of the behavioural development of school students who learn Buddhism as a core subject. It was observed that the intrinsic motivation to improve the students' behaviour through the content taught in Buddhism subject in school is lack. Patterns were built based on the observations that were recorded in various ways such as the received responses to the questionnaire, interviewing the Buddhism teachers and students, and analysing the Buddhism textbook offered to the grade 10 students. In addition to these, the students' daily attendance to school and the teachers' teaching methodologies and teaching methods were also evaluated up to a certain extent as it seemed that not only the content but also some other components might be updated parallel to optimising the syllabus. At the end of the research process, a theory was discovered regarding the effectiveness of the current syllabus for teaching Buddhism in grade 10 in schools in Sri Lanka.

In inductive perspective, the marks obtained at the most recent term test are analysed and assessed against their intrinsic achievements of learning outcomes. This is a data-

driven research. The research relies heavily on empirical data collected through questionnaires, interviews, and document analysis. This data is then analysed to identify patterns and trends, which can lead to the development of new theories or insights. The research seems to be exploratory in nature, aiming to uncover new information about the effectiveness of the Buddhism curriculum. This exploratory approach often involves inductive reasoning, as researchers start with observations and then develop generalizations based on those observations. The daily attendance of the students is also recorded and analysed. The patterns embedded in students' school attendance, term test marks, their gender specific tendency to achieving the ILOs are to be analysed and thereby patterns will be identified based on both null and alternative hypotheses. Additionally, the grade 10 Buddhism text book provided by the government is also analysed to ensure that the content is strong enough to let the students meet the intended learning outcomes stated in the syllabus.

In deductive perspective, the research was basically commenced with a set of assumptions as mentioned in the Assumptions section of the "Chapter One: Introduction". The research seems to have specific research questions and hypotheses, which are derived from existing theories and knowledge. These hypotheses had been planned to be tested using the collected data. The research is grounded in existing theories about education, curriculum development, and Buddhist philosophy. These theories provide a framework for understanding the research problem and interpreting the findings.

3.4.3 Research Strategy: Survey

The research is driven through a survey to explore the effectiveness of teaching Buddhism in school in the dimension of students' intrinsic achievement of intended learning outcomes imposed in the syllabus of grade 10.

3.4.4 Research Method: Mixed Method (Both Quantitative and Qualitative)

The employment of a mixed-methods approach, encompassing surveys, interviews, and document analysis, underscores the methodological versatility of pragmatics. This tripartite methodology was strategically selected to provide a comprehensive exploration of the study's multifaceted dimensions.

The questions in the survey were designed to collect quantitative data regarding student attitudes toward and comprehension of the Buddhism curriculum from a broad sample population of 110 students. While the data is pragmatically applied to offer a comprehensive understanding of the problem, its methodological underpinnings align with a positivist epistemological framework.

A qualitative component of this study involved follow-up interviews with twenty percent of the sample. These interviews provided an interpretivist lens through which to examine students' subjective experiences and contextual circumstances, offering nuanced insights into their evolving behaviours, cognitive processes, and personal growth trajectories.

The integration of teacher interviews into curriculum evaluation provides a valuable avenue for incorporating professional judgment and contextual understanding. This approach aligns with a pragmatic perspective that emphasizes the importance of expert input in enriching analytical endeavours.

A quantitative analysis of examination performance, rooted in a positivist epistemology, was undertaken. The intent was not merely to describe academic achievement but to interrogate the correlation between cognitive prowess and behavioural modification. A pragmatic approach was adopted to reconcile the quantitative data with qualitative insights, thereby providing a nuanced understanding of the complex interplay between academic success and desired behavioural outcomes.

This was an exploratory inductive research by which a theory was generated by the data collected. The goal was to arise the theory which reveals the reason not to achieve the intended learning outcomes of the subject intrinsically by the students in the bottom of their hearts.

The ethnography based research strategy was to execute to observe and capture the experience and perceptions of school students who learn Buddhism. The research was conducted in school in the form of an uncontrolled natural environment. Buddhism is taught in almost all the government and private schools in Sri Lanka as a bucket subject under “Religion” that acts as a core subject from grade 1 to 11. Although the subject content is delivered in schools, its influence had not been taken as the object to be systematically analysed and propose further directions to be driven the content in terms of the intended learning outcomes. This endeavour aimed to measure the effectiveness of the content delivered in the subject in a more systematic and scientific view. As it basically cope with the learners’ perception and cognition, the ethnographic research strategy was chosen.

When it comes to the time horizon of the project, it is considered as a cross-sectional data collection based research because almost all the data collected at one point within

a fortnight period through survey, interviewing and document analysis. Thematic analysis played the role of qualitative analysis while generating the descriptive statistics played the role of quantitative analysis. Additionally, the students attendance and their intrinsic development of desire to achieving the ILOs was also analysed quantitatively. An expert judgement based text book analysis was also executed during the project time frame. Moreover, the correlation in between the marks obtained in the recent term test and the students' intrinsic achievement of the ILOs was also elaborated.

Firstly, as a curriculum evaluation study, it critically examines the Buddhism syllabus, assessing its alignment with intended learning outcomes and its capacity to foster the internalization and application of Buddhist teachings.

Secondly, the study adopts a mixed-methods research design, leveraging both quantitative and qualitative methodologies. This approach enables a more nuanced understanding of the research problem by triangulating data from diverse sources, such as surveys, document analysis and interviews.

Thirdly, the study employs a descriptive and exploratory research framework, aiming to characterize the current state of the Buddhism curriculum's effectiveness and to uncover potential factors influencing student learning outcomes.

Lastly, by generating evidence-based recommendations for enhancing curriculum delivery and supporting intrinsic learning, the study contributes to the realm of educational policy and practice, providing valuable insights for policymakers and educators.

This integrative research approach, combining curriculum evaluation, mixed-methods research, descriptive and exploratory inquiry, and policy-oriented research, offers a

robust framework for addressing the complex research question and generating meaningful findings that can inform future educational practices and policies in the context of Buddhist education in Sri Lanka.

This study employed a mixed-methods research design, combining quantitative and qualitative approaches to comprehensively investigate the factors influencing the effectiveness of Buddhism education in Grade 10. A stratified random sampling technique was used to select a sample of 110 students from two schools, stratified by administrative status (semi-government and government).

Quantitative Data Collection: A structured questionnaire was administered to the selected students. This instrument comprised both closed-ended (true/false) and open-ended questions. The questionnaire was designed to assess students' knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions regarding Buddhism education, as well as their experiences with the curriculum and teaching methods. To ensure data accuracy and minimize the risk of social desirability bias, the questionnaires were administered in a supervised setting, with the researcher present to clarify any doubts. The anonymity of participants was maintained by assigning unique identification numbers to each questionnaire.

Qualitative Data Collection: A purposive sampling technique was used to select 20% of the students for in-depth interviews. These students were chosen based on their performance in a recent Buddhism term test, ensuring that they were engaged and knowledgeable about the subject matter. The interviews were conducted individually to allow for open-ended discussions and to explore participants' perspectives in greater detail. Semi-structured interview protocols were used to guide the conversation, with follow-up questions tailored to individual responses.

Document Analysis: To assess the efficacy of the Buddhism curriculum in fostering intrinsic growth, a comparative analysis was conducted between students' performance on a recent term test and their attainment of specific intended learning outcomes. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select a subset of ILOs that were deemed crucial for the holistic development of students. These ILOs were identified by carefully examining the teacher's guide and aligning them with the broader curriculum objectives. By comparing the students' test scores with their progress in achieving these selected ILOs, the study aimed to evaluate the extent to which the curriculum was successful in cultivating the desired cognitive, affective, and psychomotor skills.

By combining these research methods, the study aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors associated with the content of the syllabus influencing the effectiveness of Buddhism education in Grade 10.

3.4.5 Time Horizon: Cross-sectional

The data collection occurred only at one time although there were many methods, including questionnaire, interviewing, and document analysis through expert judgement, executed to collect data.

3.5 PARTICIPANTS

The participants for the research were basically selected by execution of a combination of both random stratified sampling technique and purposive sampling technique.

3.5.1 Sampling Strategies: Random Stratified And Purposive Sampling

The present study employed a stratified random sampling technique to select a representative sample of 110 Grade 10 students from two schools at the same town in

Anuradhapura district in Sri Lanka. The two schools were stratified based on their administrative status: semi-government and government. The semi-government school, catering to students from predominantly higher socioeconomic backgrounds, was stratified as “Group A”, while the government school, serving students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds, was stratified as “Group B”.

Within each stratum, simple random sampling was employed to select 51 students from “Group A” and 59 students from “Group B”. This approach ensured that the sample was representative of the target population, mitigating potential biases associated with systematic or convenience sampling methods. By randomly selecting participants, it was aimed to minimize the impact of extraneous variables such as academic performance, gender, and other socio-demographic factors on the study's findings. There were 42 boys and 68 girls in the sample taken from two schools.

This stratified random sampling technique provided a rigorous and statistically sound approach to sample selection, enabling the researcher to draw valid inferences about the target population of “Grade 10” students in the two schools. The government and semi-government strata are declared in this scenario. Both the strata represent only the schools offering the subject Buddhism in Sinhala medium for the grade 10 students as the Buddhism school text book of grade ten written in Sinhala medium is offered to the students by the education ministry of Sri Lanka. The content of the school text book was also analysed in this research. Because of the unavailability of the official English medium grade ten Buddhism textbook, only the schools which offer the subject in Sinhala medium were taken into consideration in the research. Therefore, the Sinhala medium schools were purposively selected according to the scope of the project, which cover only the area of the “Anuradhapura Education Zone”. The

sampling technique was not either pure purposive or pure stratified random sampling since the influence of such factors.

According to the definition of stratified random sampling, it involves dividing the population into mutually exclusive strata based on specific characteristics (e.g., school type) and then performing random sampling within each stratum. The approach executed in this endeavour drives through grouping the schools into three strata: government, semi-government and private schools. However, It was made a purposive selection of the government school and private school based on the Instructional medium that is Sinhala by which the subject Buddhism is taught. There was only one private school which offers the subject in English medium, belonging to the Anuradhapura Education Zone. The English medium school was skipped in this selection process because of its instructional medium and the less number of students.

Among all the Sinhala medium government schools, Rathnayake Vidyalaya was randomly selected. It was mostly appropriate in taking the sample from Rathnayake Vidyalaya, as the socioeconomic and academic background of many students of Rathnayake Vidyalaya were different from that of the selected semi-government school. Rathnayake Vidyalaya facilitates the students coming from five orphanages in Anuradhapura town area. Many of the families of students of Rathnayake Vidyalaya are from lower or lower middle class families. However, the selected semi-government school facilitates the students who are coming from comparatively rich families that have high level of income and their parents are also mostly well-educated and professional.

When it comes to the facilities provided in school, the selected semi-government school is prominent as there are almost all the required lab facilities, library and other

components. The students of the semi-government college are coming from high class families as the society sees. Rathnayake Vidyalaya is lack of infrastructure and other facilities required to be utilized in the teaching learning process. They did not have access to cutting-edge technologies, unlike in the semi-government college, where parents had been paying monthly installments and term fees. By introducing random selection within each stratum, the influence of personal bias in the selection process could be reduced. Since the research focused on Sinhala medium schools, the strata ensured the sample aligned with the population characteristics relevant to the study. Fair representation of school types was achieved as both the semi-government school and government school are included, providing insights into how the governance structure might influence educational practices. Therefore, using stratified sampling can be justified with the factors- representativeness, bias minimizing, alignment with research goals and fair representation of school types.

By considering all these criteria, the approach described in the case did not qualify as stratified random sampling due to the lack of randomness in the selection process. However, by modifying the method to randomly select government schools from the eligible Sinhala medium schools and automatically including the semi-government school, it could be transformed into a proper stratified random sampling technique. This method could improve the representativeness, reliability, and generalizability of the findings. Finally the sampling technique became a combination of purposive and stratified random sampling.

3.5.2 Participant Profiles: Student And Teacher

There were two types of participants as students and teachers. Their profiles were defined. Students are the ones studying Buddhism in Sinhala medium in grade 10 of

the schools selected. Teachers were the ones who teach Buddhism in Sinhala medium to those who were studying in grade 10 in the schools selected.

3.6 INSTRUMENTS OF DATA COLLECTION AND THEIR RELIABILITY

Three instruments were utilized in the research. Thereby both high quality and well quantifiable data were targetted to be gathered for analysis. Namely, they are “Questionnaire, Interviewing, and Document Analysis.

3.6.1 Questionnaire

A meticulously structured printed questionnaire was disseminated among a representative cohort of Grade 10 students to evaluate the pedagogical effectiveness of the mandated Grade 10 Buddhism textbook and its corresponding syllabus in fostering the attainment of explicitly defined Intended Learning Outcomes. The utilization of printed questionnaires for data collection from school students offers distinct advantages over online forms, particularly when considering the unique contextual and logistical challenges inherent in research involving young respondents in educational settings. For instance, accessibility can be presented. Accessibility Printed questionnaires eliminate the need for internet access, devices, and digital literacy, thereby ensuring inclusivity across all student populations, regardless of their technological resources. This approach mitigates the digital divide, particularly for students residing in rural or economically disadvantaged areas who may lack access to reliable internet or appropriate devices.

By undertaking an exhaustive quantitative analysis of the empirical data collected, the investigation sought to critically appraise the degree to which the curriculum had effectively directed learners toward the realization of these pedagogical objectives. The analytical process entailed a methodical and rigorous interrogation of student

responses to precisely gauge their proficiency and alignment with the predetermined ILO benchmarks. Each question of the questionnaire was fundamentally based on one particular unique learning outcome. Some questions were able to address the achievement of more than one ILO. All the ILOs were taken from the first 15 units which were proposed to be completed when the second term was over.

The questionnaire encompassed a total of 20 meticulously designed items, wherein 13 were dichotomous in nature, necessitating respondents to affirm or negate the presented statements by choosing "true" or "false." The remaining seven items were constructed as structured-response questions, mandating participants to not only designate their selection as "true" or "false" but also to articulate a substantiated rationale to justify their choice. Responses submitted without accompanying justifications were systematically classified as invalid, reflecting the emphasis on eliciting both cognitive affirmation and critical reasoning from the participants. Responses that lacked a justification were deemed invalid and hence they were further questioned during the individual face to face interviews with participants who got the responsibility for the answers given and finally their reasons were drawn and interpreted as either true or false. The skipped questions were also thrown in the interviews in the form of a different set of questions to get to know their uncovered reasons. During the interview, the participants had the opportunity to get clarified the given questions further. The final answers were marked as true or false under the participants' consent and permission at the end of the data collection process.

Dichotomous questions were employed in the research questionnaire, while Likert questions were not. This decision was made to leverage the simplicity and clarity of

dichotomous questions, which minimized the potential for subjective interpretation and central tendency bias.

Having been carefully considered the pros and cons of both Likert and dichotomous questions in the context of research questionnaire, Likert questions were not prompted. Likert questions act as a double-edged sword in the sense of their ordinal response scale. In the research investigating whether the Grade 10 "Buddhism" syllabus achieved its intended learning outcomes in terms of intrinsic development, the limitations of Likert-scale questions were observed when contrasted with dichotomous questions. While nuanced insights were provided by Likert questions through ordinal scales, significant challenges were posed by their inherent subjectivity in interpretation. Due to the socio-cultural diversity of the sample- comprising students from semi-government and government schools with differing socio-economic backgrounds- the variability in the interpretation of scale points was exacerbated, particularly in cross-cultural contexts, leading to potential biases.

During the analysis of student responses, a tendency for central tendency bias was identified, as neutral options were frequently selected instead of expressing strong opinions. The clarity of student views regarding whether the syllabus fostered intrinsic development was consequently obscured. Conversely, definitive insights were offered by dichotomous questions, as students were required to choose between "true" and "false" options. Ambiguity was minimized by these questions, which facilitated straightforward analysis, particularly when the alignment between questionnaire responses and verbal answers given during interviews was evaluated. This alignment was found to underscore the reliability of the data collected.

Additionally, richer data were provided by the structured dichotomous questions that required justification, as students were compelled to articulate the reasoning behind their responses. Through this approach, gaps between academic performance, as reflected in high exam scores, and the absence of observable behavioural changes were identified- a critical aspect of intrinsic development intended by the syllabus.

Thus, while subtle variations in opinion were captured by Likert questions, their disadvantages- such as susceptibility to central tendency bias and interpretive variability- were emphasized within this context. The superiority of dichotomous questions for achieving clarity and reliability in substantiating the findings was thereby underscored. These findings were utilized to propose amendments to the syllabus to align it more effectively with its intended behavioural and attitudinal outcomes.

Dichotomous questions provided a clear and concise approach. In contrast, a straightforward and unambiguous approach to data collection was provided by dichotomous questions. By requiring respondents to make binary choices, the impact of subjective interpretation and central tendency bias was minimized. This simplicity was noted to facilitate data analysis and interpretation, particularly when statistical expertise was limited. Additionally, the binary nature of dichotomous questions was found to reduce the risk of cultural misunderstandings, rendering them well-suited for cross-cultural research.

The balance between precision and simplicity was also considered in the construction of the research questionnaire. The optimal choice between Likert and dichotomous questions was determined by the specific research objectives and the required level of data granularity. While a richer and more nuanced understanding of respondents'

attitudes and perceptions was offered by Likert questions, their limitations were acknowledged and critically evaluated. Conversely, a simpler and more reliable approach was provided by dichotomous questions, particularly when the research goal necessitated the identification of clear distinctions or preferences. The questionnaire shared among the students is found in “Appendix 1” which shows each ILO related to each question.

3.6.2 Subsequent Physical Interviews

Triangulating questionnaire responses with subsequent interviews, where the same questions were posed in varied contexts and formats, could significantly enhance the depth and rigour of data collection. This methodological approach offered several advantages in ensuring the accuracy, reliability, and validity of participant responses.

- **Accuracy And Correctness**

By providing questions in a variety of situations, the research encouraged participants to engage in deeper contemplation, lowering the probability of shallow or impulsive replies. The use of different phrasings and re-framing of questions enabled the verification of answer consistency, reducing the possibility of misunderstanding or inaccurate interpretations of questionnaire items.

- **Reliability**

By rephrasing questions in multiple ways, researchers can assess the reliability and validity of participants' responses. Consistent answers across different question formulations suggest that the responses are robust and not influenced by specific wording or presentation. Conversely, inconsistent responses may indicate ambiguity in the questions or variability in participants' interpretations.

- **Trustworthiness**

Engaging participants in interviews facilitated a dialogic process, enabling researchers to delve deeper into the rationale behind responses and uncover nuanced insights that might elude static questionnaire formats. This dynamic interaction enhanced the authenticity of responses by mitigating the potential for socially desirable or inattentive answers often associated with self-report measures.

To mitigate the challenges associated with combining interviews with questionnaire, various strategies were implemented. To manage time and resources by ensuring efficient planning and creating a detailed schedule along with sufficient time allocation for interviews caused to ensure that the process aligning with research timelines. Interviewer's bias was minimized by maintaining the consistency across interviews through developing an interview guide with clearly defined prompts and following up questions along with natural phrasing. The interpretation of questions caused to ensure consistency. A pre-test was done to pilot the interview questions with a small subset of participants to identify and resolve ambiguities or variations in interpretation. Contextual anchoring also came into play by clearly explaining the purpose of rephrased questions and ensuring that they retain the original intent. Additionally, member checking process also was running during the interviews. It is summarising the participants' responses during the interview and seeking their confirmation to ensure accurate interpretation. To address the analytical complexity, coding frameworks were developed. Thereby it was easier to categorize responses systematically and facilitate comparison between questionnaire and interview data. To maximizing participant engagement, participants were informed about the purpose of the dual approach and reassure them of confidentiality to encourage honest and thoughtful responses. Flexible scheduling caused to accommodate participants'

availability to reduce potential stress or fatigue during interviews. The methodological challenges were successfully navigated through the strategic integration of interviews and questionnaires, culminating in a robust and credible research process that significantly enhanced the validity, reliability, and depth of the findings.

3.6.3 Document Analysis

Document analysis was driven in three dimensions.

1. Students' school attendance report
2. Students' recent term test marks scored for Buddhism subject
3. Grade 10 Buddhism textbook analysis

Firstly, the certified school attendance reports of the Grade 10 students were gathered and analysed to verify the continuous attendance of the sample population. This analysis aimed at investigating the potential correlation between student attendance and the achievement of intended learning outcomes in Buddhism, which are crucial for the intrinsic behavioural development of Grade 10 students.

Secondly, the mark analysis was done. The most recently conducted term test marks were collected for analysis to determine the correlation between the scores attained and the extent of achievement of the Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs). A total of 29 unique ILOs, designated for attainment by the conclusion of the second term, were identified and evaluated. The term test scores of each student were systematically compared with the quantified metrics representing the achievement levels of the ILOs, as assessed through responses to the questionnaire and the outcomes of the interviews.

Thirdly, the textbook was analysed as per the applicability of achieving the intended learning outcomes mentioned in the syllabus. This attempt was to inspect whether all the units deliver pure Dhamma or promoting misconceptions or malpractices which

might lead the learner towards anywhere except “*Nibbana*”. The alignment between the contents of the Grade 10 Buddhism textbook and the expected learning outcomes (ELOs) was analysed through the application of expert judgment method. This method involved leveraging the expertise of subject matter specialists, curriculum developers, and experienced educators to assess the extent to which the textbook material contributed to the achievement of the ELOs. By referring to the *Tipitaka*, the contents that seemed to be incorrect, inappropriate and misinterpreted were revised. It ensured the reliability of the reported cases received as a result of textbook analysis effort executed by employing the expert judgement method. There were two subject experts, Mr. N.K. Karunasekara who is a teacher of Vipassana meditation and Mr. P. Gunarathne who is a Vipassana meditation practitioner having the academic qualification of “Master of Philosophy”. The whole research was conducted under the guidance of the supervisor of the research Dr. S.A.R.R.P. Dissanayake who is a senior lecturer of Gampaha Wickramarachchi University of Indigenous Medicine and the most venerable Karapikkada Sobitha Thero who is a senior lecturer of the Bhikshu University of Sri Lanka.

3.7 METHODOLOGICAL LIMITATIONS AND SOLUTIONS

No research design or methodology is perfect. There will always be trade-offs between the ideal design and the design that is practical and viable given the constraints. While the research was going on, following limitations had to be addressed.

- Lack of time
- Budget constraints
- Sampling issues

- Analysis method limitations
- Dealing with incomplete documentations and records

Each of the above issues were pragmatically solved by executing various systems as mentioned below.

Since the research was conducted to fulfil the requirement of the university to receive it as an input to the academic qualification of Master of Education, the researcher had to accomplish all the tasks related to the project within a six month period. As a result, the size of sample of students also was reduced to 110 whom was qualified to answer the survey questionnaire and out of those students only 20 students were called for in-depth interviews. Besides, the budget allocated to the entire research was not sufficient to take a larger sample which could have to be treated if there was a possibility to find a sponsor who was interested in the aims of the research. Only two schools from the same town which belong to the Anuradhapura education zone was selected to mitigate the transport and printing cost for sharing the questionnaire among the students of a number of schools scattered throughout the district as thought prior to the commencement of the research. Assigning the students for interviews and exposing them to questionnaire given in the survey were difficult due to the fixed time schedules in schools. Allocating students for such a project was a critical decision to be made by the principals of the schools selected although the research was approved and beneficial. Therefore the sample was taken from two schools only. One is a government school while the other is a semi-government school which is supervised under the private school division of the ministry of education of Sri Lanka. Besides all the costs, the paid software were also to be used to analyse the data collected. To mitigate the software cost, open source software tools such as PSPP

were used. SPSS was also used for a fixed short period. Additionally, free versions of commercially available data analysis tools like “NVIVO” were used for a limited period of time. The application “NVIVO” supported to analyse qualitative data in the form of thematic analysis while the PSPP was utilized to analyse quantitative data. In addition, LibreOffice Writer was used in preparation of excerpts and themes in thematic analysis process.

3.8 PROCEDURES OF STUDY (RESEARCH PROCESS)

Step 1: Observation

Initially, it was observed that students must acquire various skills and practices intended to be cultivated through the systematic teaching of Buddhism in schools.

Step 2: Review Of Syllabus and Textbooks

A detailed examination of the Buddhism syllabi and textbooks revealed that, while students engage with Buddhism as a formal subject, they often fail to achieve the ILOs articulated in the curriculum.

Step 3: Conceptualization Of Research

The preliminary insights led to the formulation of a research study aimed at identifying the issues underlying the delivery of Buddhism content to school students and evaluating the alignment between the curriculum and the achieved outcomes.

Step 4: Selection Of Research Sample

A total of 110 Grade 10 students were purposively selected as the research sample. This cohort represented both male and female students from two schools within the Anuradhapura Education Zone: a semi-government college and a government school. Although there was only one private school offering Buddhism for Grade 10 students

in English medium within the region, it was excluded from the study for the following reasons.

1. Small class sizes of Grade 10 students
2. Non-adherence to the local curriculum and/or Sinhala medium
3. Limited representation of students.

Step 5: Ethical Considerations And Consent

The parents and guardians of the selected students were informed about the research objectives and the participation of their children. This communication was facilitated by the class teachers through verbal messages under the principals' authorization. A formal introductory letter, issued by the principal of the researcher's school, was provided to the principals of the selected schools to seek permission for data collection. The letter introduced the researcher, who is a teacher pursuing a Master of Education degree, and outlined the project's objectives and methods. Participation in the study was voluntary, with all students willingly engaging in the data collection process.

Step 6: Design Of Assessment Tools

The research focused on 35 ILOs outlined in the Buddhism syllabus for the first two terms of Grade 10. Of these, 29 ILOs were selected as the basis for creating evaluation instruments. These included 13 true/false questions and 7 structured essay questions designed to assess students' intrinsic motivation and alignment with the ILOs. The questionnaire was distributed among the sample students following formal approval from the school principals, granted after a presentation of the research proposal and introductory letter.

Step 7: Student Interviews

A supplementary set of interview questions, based on the 29 selected ILOs, was prepared for one-on-one interviews with students who had previously completed the questionnaire. These interviews aimed to gain deeper insights into the students' perceptions and motivations.

Step 8: Teacher Interviews

An additional set of questions was developed for the Buddhism teachers instructing the sampled students. Five teachers participated in the study, providing their perspectives on the curriculum, its alignment with the ILOs, and the delivery of content in classrooms. During interviews conducted with the teachers in their respective school premises, several behavioural challenges associated with students were also reported. These interviews were carried out with the principals' consent and in accordance with institutional guidelines.

Step 9: Analysis Of Academic Performance

The term test scores of the sampled students in Buddhism were collected with the assistance of the school administration and class teachers. These scores were recorded and organized for analysis using a spreadsheet application.

Step 10: Attendance Data Collection

Attendance records for the sampled students were obtained from the class attendance registers for the first two terms of the academic year. This data, gathered under the supervision of class teachers, was entered into a spreadsheet for further analysis. All data collection activities were conducted during the third term of the academic year 2024. At the end of the data collection process, a special group discussion was held to share the experience of the students on the research that was being conducted with them. They expressed that they were satisfied with the answers provided in the

interviews and for the questions found in the questionnaire and hence it was proven that the data are at an acceptable level and it assures the reliability and validity of data as well. This methodological framework ensured a comprehensive investigation into the effectiveness of the Buddhism curriculum and its impact on achieving the desired learning outcomes among Grade 10 students.

3.9 RELIABILITY PROCEDURES

Both qualitative and quantitative data were collected through 3 mechanisms – questionnaire, interviewing, and document analysis. The questionnaire was enriched with scenario-based or situational analysis questions to measure the effectiveness of students' higher order thinking capacity and practical applicability of the content of the syllabus of Buddhism of grade 10. Since the questions targeting the level of memory recalling ability of the students were lack in the questionnaire, it was a novel experience for almost all the students in the sample taken as they expressed their ideas on the research attempt at the group discussions held as the last event of the data collection process.

3.9.1 Reliability Of Responses Received For Questionnaire

A printed questionnaire was given to the sample of students while they were studying in school. The researcher and the students' Buddhism teacher were observing them and supported them when they needed further clarifications while answering the questions. Printed questionnaire was worth in this case due to many reasons which are briefly presented herein.

Printed questionnaires minimize distractions. Printed forms can create a focused environment, minimizing distractions from digital devices and potentially enhancing

student engagement by encouraging deeper concentration and more thoughtful responses.

The use of paper-based assessments can promote honest responses by fostering a sense of perceived anonymity. Students may be more inclined to share candid opinions when writing on paper, as they may perceive printed forms to be less traceable than digital submissions, which could potentially be monitored or misused. This suggests that paper-based assessments can mitigate digital mistrust and encourage more authentic student feedback.

The administration of printed questionnaires in a classroom setting facilitates enhanced monitoring and supervision by allowing teachers or researchers to directly oversee the completion process, thereby mitigating the potential for collaboration or omission of questions. Furthermore, the presence of an instructor or researcher on-site enables immediate clarification of any ambiguities or uncertainties that may arise among participants.

Printed questionnaires mitigate technical challenges by eliminating the potential for internet connectivity issues, device malfunctions, and compatibility problems inherent in online forms. Additionally, they accommodate students with varying levels of technological proficiency, as paper-based surveys require no prior experience with online survey tools.

Printed questionnaires offer a more inclusive approach for students who may not yet possess the digital literacy necessary for navigating online forms or for those who may have special needs that necessitate adaptations, such as larger fonts or simplified layouts, which can be more readily accommodated in print formats.

Printed questionnaires offer tangible advantages in data collection, providing a physical record of responses that can be archived and referenced independently of digital storage. This tangible format also facilitates immediate verification, as researchers can visually inspect completed questionnaires to ensure comprehensive responses and identify any omissions.

The physical distribution and collection of printed questionnaires facilitate direct interaction between researchers and students, thereby fostering trust and rapport. Additionally, the tactile experience of writing responses can enhance engagement for some students compared to digital modes of input, such as clicking or typing.

Online surveys may inadvertently exclude students lacking technological access, potentially skewing results and limiting the representativeness of the sample. To mitigate this bias and ensure a comprehensive representation of the school population, printed questionnaires can be utilized to capture the perspectives of all demographic groups.

3.9.2 Reliability Of Data Collected Through Interviews

The questionnaire responses were triangulated with interviews, where the same questions were asked in different contexts and formats. This approach was used to increase the depth and rigour of data collection. Several advantages were provided to ensure the accuracy, reliability, and validity of the participants' responses.

Participants were engaged in interviews, and a dialogic process was facilitated. Researchers were enabled to explore the reasons behind responses and uncover deeper insights that were missed by static questionnaires. The authenticity of responses was enhanced, and the potential for socially desirable or inattentive answers was reduced.

The interview questions were piloted with a small group of participants in a pre-test to identify and fix any ambiguities or misunderstandings. The purpose of the rephrased questions was clearly explained to ensure that their original meaning was kept.

3.9.3 Reliability Of Data Collected Through Document Analysis

Both the records of marks obtained for Buddhism subject at the recent term test and students' attendance reports were collected from the authorized personnel of the schools with the consent of the principals. Grade 10 Buddhism text book offers to the students from the government. The printed syllabus of grade 10 Buddhism subject was accessed from the school.

Additionally, the “*Sambuddha Jayanthi Tipitaka Grantha Mala*” also was accessed to be referred to the required “*Sutta*” to ensure the correctness and accuracy of the text book analysis performed by the two subject experts employed in the research.

3.10 DATA ANALYSIS OF STUDY

The analysis of data employed both quantitative and qualitative methods. Quantitative analysis was used to examine term test marks and questionnaire responses through statistical techniques to identify trends and patterns. Qualitative analysis, on the other hand, was conducted on interview data using thematic coding to uncover underlying themes and patterns in the responses. To further enhance the analysis, a comparative approach was used to examine the relationship between students' academic performance and their observed behavioural outcomes. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) and NVivo were utilized as tools to facilitate the analysis process.

By simply going through the data collected through the formal scientific procedures, 5 null hypotheses and 8 alternative hypotheses were developed.

3.10.1 Null Hypotheses:

1. NH 1: There is no significant relationship between students' school attendance rate and their intrinsic achievement of the Intended Learning Outcomes.
2. NH 2: There is no significant difference in the intrinsic achievement of the ILOs between male and female students.
3. NH 3: There is no significant relationship between students' term test marks and their intrinsic achievement of the ILOs.
4. NH 4: There is no significant difference in the intrinsic achievement of the ILOs between students who study in different types of schools with various facilities and infrastructure.
5. NH 5: There is no significant difference in the intrinsic achievement of the ILOs between students taught using different methodologies and methods.

3.10.2 Alternate Hypotheses

1. AH 1: The content of the school textbook, as determined by expert judgmental review, fails to motivate and enable students to intrinsically embrace the ILOs due to misleading information and misconceptions about the pure Dhamma.
2. AH 2: The classroom content is not sufficiently practical to facilitate students' understanding of the pure Dhamma.
3. AH 3: The textbook content prioritizes Buddhist history and literature over the direct delivery of the pure Dhamma to students.
4. AH 4: The Grade 10 Buddhism syllabus is overly exam-oriented, neglecting the development of intrinsic understanding of the subject matter.

5. AH 5: Teachers' lack of continuous Vipassana practice hinders their ability to motivate students to explore the Four Noble Truths, as the practice provides a means to experience these truths first-hand.
6. AH 6: Teachers' limited knowledge of the Pali language negatively impacts students' intrinsic achievement of the ILOs.
7. AH 7: Teachers' inadequate knowledge of Tipitaka Studies leads to misinterpretation of textbook content, which hinders students' intrinsic achievement of the ILOs.
8. AH 8: The content of the syllabus and textbook does not align with the intended learning outcomes.

3.11 QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS

The quantitative analysis on the responses gathered from the questionnaire was performed at six dimensions.

3.11.1 Dimension 1: Students' ILO Achievement Rate

The categorical data "ILO_Grade" had five categories as A, B, C, S and W. The relevant ILO_Grade was assigned to each student based on the "ILO_Rate" which was calculated by applying the formula shown in "Figure 4":

$$\text{ILO Rate} = \frac{Y}{(Y+N)} \times 100\%$$

Figure 4: ILO_Rate Calculation

where, the variable Y is the number of occurrences at which a particular participant's answer given for a question could be aligned with the relevant ILO as prescribed in the syllabus. N represents the number of occurrences at which the participant's answer given for the question did not align with the relevant ILO. Every question had been

compiled according to a specific ILO. If the ILO_Rate is greater than or equal to 75%, then the ILO_Grade becomes “A”. If the ILO_Rate is in between 74% and 65% including both the boundary values, then the ILO_Grade becomes “B”. If the ILO_Rate is in between 64% and 55% including both the boundary values, then the ILO_Grade becomes “C”. If the ILO_Rate is in between 54% and 35% including both the boundary values, then the ILO_Grade becomes “S”. If the ILO_Rate is less than 35%, then the ILO_Grade becomes “W”. The maximum allowed ILO_Rate was 100% while the minimum was 0%. Thus the achievement rate of the ILOs was calculated for each student separately and divided them into the relevant 5 categories – “A, B, C, S, and W” which represent “Excellent, Very Good, Good, Satisfied, and Weak”, respectively.

Assigning the ILO_Grade for each student was done by following the process of assigning binary values (zero or one) for each response received from each participant. The responses collected from sharing the questionnaire among the selected crowd, was quantitatively analysed to identify the effectiveness of achieving the ILOs. The total number of questions was 20, 7 out of which were structured essay questions. However, the responses to the structured essay questions were also converted into a binary value as zero or one. In case of the answer which had satisfied the intended learning outcome, then the answer was taken as 1 or “True”, otherwise it was 0 or “False”. Participants’ responses for some structured essay questions were highlighted for further reference. Based on the responses given for the questions, a numeric value was generated for each question according to the binary logic which stated 1 or “True” if the response indicated that the student had achieved the ILO evaluated by the particular question, and otherwise 0 or “False”. The percentage of

achieving the learning outcome is taken by dividing the addition of the numeric values set to each question in the questionnaire given to a particular student, by 100 and then it is expressed as a percentage. If someone scores 20 out of 20, the rate of the candidates' achievement of considered intended learning outcome will be recorded as 100 percent.

Student ID	ILO Rate	ILO Grade
1		
2		
3		
4		

Figure 5: ILO_Rate And ILO_Grade

The ILO_Rates recorded in the format given in “Figure 5” are further categorised into five classes as A, B, C, S, and W representing “Excellent, Very Good, Good, Satisfactory, and Weak” respectively. Then the number of students belonging to each class is found. Eventually, it is expressed as a percentage.

Then the total number of each ILO_Grade was taken separately to be applied on the formula shown in “Figure 6”:

$$\text{ILO_Grade_Percentage} = \frac{{}_nS}{\text{tot}P} \times 100\%$$

Figure 6: ILO_Grade_Percentage

where, ${}_nS$ represented the number of students who got the particular ILO_Grade, and $\text{tot}P$ represented the total number of participants that was 110, to find the “ILO_Grade_Percentage” of each “ILO_Grade” out of the whole sample.

ILO Grade	No. of Students	ILO Grade Percentage
A		
B		
C		
S		
W		

Figure 7: No. of Students Vs. ILO_Grade_Percentage

3.11.2 Dimension 2: The Achievement Rate Of Each ILO

The responses received for each question in the questionnaire was analysed along with the addition of the numeric values scored by all the students. If a student marked an answer which aligned to the relevant ILO was recorded as 1. Likewise, after adding all the “one”s coming under each ILO were separately calculated. Then it was divided by the total number of participants and the result was expressed in the form of percentage. The result was calculated for each question separately by using the formula shown in “Figure 8”:

$$\text{The Achievement Rate of Each ILO} = \frac{_{pn}S}{_{tot}P} \times 100\%$$

Figure 8: The Achievement Rate Of Each ILO

where, $_{pn}S$ represents the number of students who could gain mark 1 for a particular question that is based on a certain ILO, and $_{tot}P$ represented the total number of participants which was 110.

3.11.3 Dimension 3: Attendance Vs. Overall ILO Achievement

A comparison between the percentage of attendance and the percentage of achievement of ILOs was performed to clarify whether the selected variables are related to each other in any manner or they are totally independent from each other.

Student ID	Attendance Rate	ILO Rate
1		
2		
.		
.		
110		

Figure 9: Attendance_Rate Vs. ILO_Rate

The schools were held for 124 days during the period of the first and second terms in the academic year 2024. The Attendance_Rate was calculated as a percentage by applying the formula shown in “Figure 10”,

$$\text{Attendance_Rate of Each Student} = \frac{\text{days Attended}}{\text{days Held}} \times 100\%$$

Figure 10: Attendance_Rate of Each Student

where, days Attended represented the number of days the particular student was present in the school, and days Held represented the total number of days the school was held that was 124.

A chi-squared test of independence was performed to evaluate the statistical significance of the relationship between the categorical variables – attendance rate and the rate of overall achievement of the ILOs.

3.11.4 Dimension 4: Term Test Score Vs. Each Student’s Overall ILO Achievement

The relationship in between the term test score and the achievement rate of ILOs were analysed to find whether they were mutually exclusive or not. The marks obtained by each student of the sample for the subject at the most recent term test that was their

second term test in grade 10, was taken into consideration with the hope of keeping the limits of the research.

Student_ID	Term Test Marks	ILO_Rate
1		
2		
.		
.		
.		
110		

Figure 11: Term_Test_Marks Vs. ILO_Rate

A Chi-square test was executed to inspect whether the variables – “Term Test Marks and ILO_Rate” are dependent on each other or independent from each other.

3.11.5 Dimension 5: Gender Vs. Overall ILO Achievement

A chi-squared test of independence was employed to determine whether a statistical association exists between the categorical variables – “Gender and ILO_Rate”. The analysis was driven for identification of evidence for any relationship laying down between the gender and the achievement of ILOs of students.

3.11.6 Dimension 6: School Type Vs. Overall ILO Achievement

The analysis was driven for identification of evidence for any relationship laying down between the students’ achievement of ILOs of the selected schools to indicate whether the factor of available facilities for teaching Buddhism has influenced in students’ ILO achievement. Assuming that the students’ family backgrounds and socio-cultural aspects of their living community do appear as significant factors of achieving the ILOs, it is clear that the content of the Buddhism syllabus does not actively contribute itself to motivate the students achieve the ILOs as expected by the government through the delivery of the lessons in Buddhism syllabus.

A Chi-square test was run to explore the fact of being a relationship between the two variables and this effort was fruitful as a random stratified sample had been taken by considering the facilities provided in school, the range of socio-economic background of the participants, access to the cutting edge technologies etcetera.

3.12 QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

Qualitative analysis was conducted across three dimensions: an analysis of student responses to the questionnaire, an analysis of teacher interview responses, and an expert review of the Grade 10 Buddhism textbook.

3.12.1 Dimension 1: Thematic Analysis Of Students' Responses To The Questionnaire

Analysing the responses obtained for structured essay type questions in the questionnaire presented to the students, is illustrated with the technique of thematic analysis. It is applicable for the structured essay type questions ranging from 14th question to the 20th question. Appendix 1 holds the questions in questionnaire, the ILOs related to each question and the content delivered to guide the students to reach the relevant ILOs.

3.12.1.1 Thematic Analysis Of 14th Question:

According to the textbook and stressed in the syllabus, the correct order of the four noble truths is "*dukkha arya satya, dukkha samudaya arya satya, dukkha nirodha arya satya and finally dukkha nirodha gamini patipada arya satya*". It is said that there's a famous saying which states that the order of the four noble truths should be as follows: "*dukkha arya satya, dukkha samudaya satya, dukkha nirodha gamini patipada arya satya, and finally dukkha nirodha arya satya*". Do you agree with the so-called famous saying? Come up with your reasons.

Three themes were developed based on the responses received from the students.

Theme 1: Adherence To Tradition

A notable subset of respondents exhibited a pronounced allegiance to the canonical sequence prescribed by the textbook, perceiving it as the definitive framework for understanding the Four Noble Truths. This perspective is rooted in the belief that the prescribed order mirrors the inherent logical progression and doctrinal purity of the Buddhist tradition. As one participant asserted,

"The textbook order is correct because *dukkha nirodha* must precede *dukkha nirodha gamini patipada*. Without a prior understanding of the cessation of suffering, comprehending the path to its cessation becomes untenable."

This unwavering adherence to the established curriculum underscores a profound deference to institutionalized knowledge. For these students, the textbook emerges as an uncontested repository of truth, thereby privileging rote learning and canonical fidelity over critical inquiry. Such a response pattern may be attributable to the influence of formal pedagogy, which often prioritizes a didactic approach that emphasizes the transmission of established knowledge over the cultivation of independent thought.

Theme 2: Support For Logical Order

Conversely, a significant portion of respondents expressed support for the alternative order, aligning with the famous saying's emphasis on a perceived logical progression. They interpreted this sequence as reflecting a more pragmatic approach that mirrors the experiential journey of understanding and transcending suffering. As one participant stated,

"Yes, I agree with the famous saying because the steps seem logical. First, we learn about suffering, then its cause, the way to stop it, and finally experience its cessation."

This preference for a logical sequence suggests a process-oriented cognitive style, whereby participants prioritize the sequential unfolding of insights as they relate to real-world application. It indicates that these students are more inclined towards frameworks that emphasize causality and practical pathways to realization. This inclination may be influenced by contemporary pedagogical approaches that prioritize critical thinking, problem-solving, and experiential learning.

Theme 3: Uncertainty And Cognitive Gaps

A subset of respondents exhibited an inability to articulate a definitive stance, often citing a lack of comprehension. As one participant candidly noted,

"No opinion, because I don't fully understand the difference between the two orders."

This theme reveals significant cognitive gaps, potentially indicative of pedagogical shortcomings or insufficient emphasis on cultivating critical engagement with doctrinal content. It raises questions about the effectiveness of the curriculum in fostering deeper conceptual clarity and its capacity to inspire intrinsic understanding of the Dhamma.

Conclusion Of Responses Of 14th Question

The findings reveal a spectrum of student engagement with Buddhist doctrinal teachings, ranging from rigid adherence to traditional interpretations to nuanced, context-sensitive understandings. While some students demonstrated a deep appreciation for the doctrinal subtleties and their practical applications, others

exhibited significant cognitive gaps, particularly in their ability to critically analyse and synthesize information. This suggests potential limitations in the current curriculum's ability to balance doctrinal fidelity with critical inquiry.

3.12.1.2 Thematic Analysis Of 15th Question:

Thematic Analysis Report for the question - "Do you believe that studying the Lord Buddha's lotus-like life has contributed to your own inner purification? Provide evidence."

Following excerpts were recorded.

Excerpt 1:

"Yes, waking up early in the morning and doing my morning ablution are done as I have studied the Lord Buddha's lotus-like life."

Excerpt 2:

"No, I don't think it has changed me much because I don't fully understand how to apply these teachings to my life."

Excerpt 3:

"Yes, living and rising as a good Buddhist disciple in the society which is full of defilements."

Excerpt 4:

"Yes, when there are challenges to be won."

Coding in Thematic Analysis

Coding went through 6 steps.

Step 1: Being Familiar With The Ideas Recorded

Responses were reviewed multiple times to extract recurring ideas and unique perspectives. Particular attention was paid to how the Buddha's life is understood and its impact on students' behaviour and attitudes.

Step 2: Generating Initial Codes

Table 1: Codes Table 1

Excerpt	Initial Code
Excerpt 1	<i>Waking up early, doing morning ablution</i>
Excerpt 2	<i>Don't fully understand, difficulty in application</i>
Excerpt 3	<i>Living as a good Buddhist disciple, social betterment</i>
Excerpt 4	<i>Overcoming challenges, resilience</i>

Step 3: Searching For Themes

Initial codes were categorized into broader themes that reflect the participants' experiences.

Table 2: Codes Table 2

Themes	Codes	Excerpts
Misunderstanding	<i>Waking up early, doing morning ablution</i>	Excerpts 1
Impracticality	<i>Don't fully understand, difficulty in application</i>	Excerpts 2
Social Development	<i>Living as a good Buddhist disciple, social betterment</i>	Excerpts 3
Resilience through Challenges	<i>Overcoming challenges, resilience</i>	Excerpt 4

Step 4: Reviewing Themes

Themes were validated by checking for coherence and consistency across all excerpts. For instance, "Impracticality" captures the inability to translate the teachings into real-

life scenarios, while "Resilience through Challenges" emphasizes using the teachings as a motivational framework to overcome difficulties.

Step 5: Defining and Naming Themes

- **Misunderstanding:** Highlights superficial engagement with the concept of the Buddha's lotus-like life, leading to partial or misguided interpretations.
- **Impracticality:** Reflects students' struggles to integrate theoretical teachings into practical life due to insufficient contextual examples.
- **Social Development:** Captures insights into how the teachings inspire students to contribute positively to their community and live ethically.
- **Resilience through Challenges:** Shows how students internalize the Buddha's life lessons to cultivate strength and perseverance in facing life's adversities.

Step 6: Producing The Report

The finding of the 15th ILO is considered herein.

Theme 1: Misunderstanding

Participants often cited routine actions, such as waking up early or performing ablutions, as outcomes of studying the Buddha's life. However, these responses suggest a limited or superficial understanding of the concept. The connection to inner purification appears tangential, as these practices lack deeper alignment with the ethical and spiritual dimensions of the teachings.

Theme 2: Impracticality

Some participants acknowledged that studying the Buddha's life had little to no effect on their behaviour. This was attributed to the lack of practical examples provided in the classroom. Without real-life scenarios to contextualize the teachings, students

struggled to comprehend or apply the Buddha's lifestyle to their own lives, as one participant had clearly and directly said that his idea on the matter of concern is: *"I don't fully understand how to apply these teachings to my life."*

Theme 3: Social Development

A subset of students demonstrated a deeper grasp of the teachings, focusing on their role as ethical and responsible individuals within society. These participants viewed the Buddha's life as a guide for navigating societal challenges and rising above moral defilements, suggesting that the teachings helped foster a sense of accountability and moral leadership.

Theme 4: Accepting Challenges

Some students perceived the Buddha's life as a source of strength during difficult times. They highlighted the Buddha's ability to overcome adversities as a motivating factor in developing their own resilience. This theme suggests that the teachings resonate as a framework for emotional and moral fortitude.

Summary of the thematic analysis of the 15th question:

The thematic analysis revealed significant variations in how students perceive the impact of studying the Lord Buddha's lotus-like life:

1. Misunderstanding often led to a superficial interpretation of the teachings.
2. Impracticality highlighted a gap between theory and application, indicating the need for improved teaching methods.
3. Social Development showcased how some students used the teachings to develop ethical and social skills.
4. Resilience through Challenges demonstrated the Buddha's life as an inspiring model for perseverance.

Conclusion of Responses gained for the 15th Question:

Not all students reported achieving the intended learning outcomes. While some found the teachings transformative, many struggled with comprehension or application. This underscores the importance of integrating contextual, real-life examples into the curriculum to bridge theoretical knowledge with practical understanding. Strengthening pedagogical strategies can enhance the students' ability to internalize and apply the lessons from the Buddha's life, fostering intrinsic moral and spiritual development.

3.12.1.3 Thematic Analysis of 16th Question:

To what extent did memorizing the Buddhist verses "*Acaritvā brahmacariyam*" and "*uttanawato satimato*" written in Dhammapada contribute to your ability to manage your time effectively and efficiently?

The responders were in a wide range and the most common excerpts are analysed herein with the use of thematic analysis technique.

Excerpt 1: "Yeah, I'm getting better at planning my day and not being lazy. I learned this from those verses."

Excerpt 2: "Nope, I memorized the verses but it didn't really change how I use my time."

Excerpt 3: "Yeah, the verses help me wake up early and stay focused all day."

Excerpt 4: "I don't think it helped much because I didn't really understand what the verses meant."

Excerpt 5: "Yeah, I feel more responsible with my time now. The verses make me want to live more mindfully."

After familiarizing the data gathered through the questionnaire, each excerpt was coded to identify meaningful concepts.

Table 3: Codes Table 3

Excerpt	Initial Codes
Excerpt 1	Planning tasks, avoiding laziness
Excerpt 2	Memorized but no impact
Excerpt 3	Waking up early, staying focused
Excerpt 4	Lack of understanding
Excerpt 5	Feeling responsible, living mindfully

Codes were grouped into broader themes to reflect the essence of the responses.

Table 4: Codes Table 4

Themes	Codes	Excerpts
Improved Time Management	Planning tasks, avoiding laziness, waking up early, staying focused	Excerpts 1, 3, 5
No Significant Impact	Memorized but no impact	Excerpt 2
Lack of Understanding	Lack of understanding	Excerpt 4

Themes were reviewed for consistency and validity, ensuring they accurately represent participants' perspectives. Then the themes were defined and named as follows.

- **Improved Time Management:** Participants who found the verses effective for organizing their time and enhancing focus.

- No Significant Impact: Participants who memorized the verses but did not experience any practical changes.
- Lack of Understanding: Participants who could not apply the verses' teachings due to limited comprehension.

A deeper analysis of the excerpts have been conducted and the following explanations on each theme identified are presented as a result of that effort.

Theme 1: Improved Time Management (Enhanced Mindfulness And Self-Discipline)

The first theme, improved time management, is a direct manifestation of the Buddhist concept of mindfulness. By memorizing and reflecting on the verses, students may have cultivated a heightened awareness of their thoughts, emotions, and actions. This increased mindfulness can lead to better self-regulation and a more disciplined approach to time management.

The verses, particularly "*uttanawato satimato*," emphasize the importance of early rising and mindful living. By internalizing these teachings, students may have developed a stronger sense of purpose and motivation, enabling them to prioritize tasks and avoid procrastination.

Theme 2: No Significant Impact (The Limitations of Rote Memorization)

The second theme, the lack of significant impact, underscores the limitations of rote memorization. While memorization can be a useful tool for learning, it is not sufficient for true understanding and application. Without a deep understanding of the underlying principles and values, students may struggle to integrate the teachings into their daily lives.

To maximize the benefits of such practices, educators should encourage students to engage in critical thinking and reflection. By asking questions, discussing the meaning of the verses, and exploring real-world applications, students can develop a more nuanced understanding of the teachings.

Theme 3: Lack Of Understanding (The Importance Of Meaningful Interpretation)

The third theme, the lack of understanding, highlights the importance of meaningful interpretation. If students do not comprehend the deeper meaning of the verses, they are unlikely to derive any significant benefits.

To address these challenges, educators should consider adopting innovative pedagogical approaches that emphasize experiential learning and critical thinking. By incorporating techniques such as meditation, guided imagery, and group discussions, students can gain a more profound understanding of the verses and their relevance to their lives.

Conclusion Of Responses Received For The 16th Question

In conclusion, while memorization can be a useful tool, it is essential to complement it with meaningful interpretation and experiential learning. By fostering a deeper understanding of Buddhist philosophy, educators can empower students to harness the transformative potential of these ancient teachings.

3.12.1.4 Thematic Analysis Of 17th Question:

"Were there any situations at which you had thought to do something wrong but you refrained from doing it due to the facts regarding karma as discussed in the 12th lesson of grade 10 Buddhism textbook in the form of cause and effect?"

List of Excerpts:

Excerpt 1: "Yes. when a mosquito bites me, I refrained from killing it although I could kill it."

Excerpt 2: "Yes, when I wanted to blame someone, I did not do so as I believe in Kamma."

Excerpt 3: "Yes. But the particular lesson has no any positive influence to do so."

Excerpt 4: "No, I do not have any specific reason to say so."

Excerpt 5: "Yes, but I don't have any specific occasion to be described."

Step 1: Data Familiarization

The responses were read and re-read to identify patterns and recurring ideas related to the lesson's influence on students' behaviour and intrinsic motivation.

Step 2: Initial Coding

A rigorous thematic analysis was conducted on the student responses. The data was meticulously examined to identify recurring patterns and salient themes. Initial coding involved the categorization of excerpts based on key concepts and phrases, such as "karma," "moral behaviour," and "lesson impact."

Table 5: Codes Table 5

Excerpt	Initial Codes
Excerpt 1	Refraining from killing, belief in karma
Excerpt 2	Avoiding blame, belief in karma
Excerpt 3	No positive influence of the lesson
Excerpt 4	No specific reason, no impact
Excerpt 5	No specific occasion, general belief

Step 3: Searching For Themes

The codes were grouped into broader themes to reflect the key insights.

Table 6: Codes Table 6

Themes	Codes	Excerpts
Behavioural Changes due to Karma	Refraining from killing, avoiding blame	Excerpts 1, 2
No Influence of Lesson	No positive influence of the lesson	Excerpt 3
Lack of Specificity	No specific reason, no specific occasion	Excerpts 4, 5

Step 4: Reviewing Themes

The themes were reviewed for consistency and alignment with the research objective, ensuring they adequately reflect the data.

Step 5: Defining And Naming Themes

1. Behavioural Changes due to Karma: Reflects students who reported actions aligned with karma's principles but not necessarily influenced by the lesson.
2. No Influence of Lesson: Highlights the lack of direct impact from the lesson on students' intrinsic motivation to refrain from wrongdoing.
3. Lack of Specificity: Indicates vague or generic responses, suggesting a superficial understanding or limited application of the lesson.

Step 6: Theme Identification And Refinement

Through a systematic process of grouping and refining codes, three primary themes emerged.

1. **Karma-Influenced Behaviour:** This theme encompasses student responses that suggest actions influenced by the principle of karma, such as refraining from killing or avoiding blame. While these behaviours align with the teachings of karma, the direct impact of the specific lesson remains unclear.
2. **Limited Lesson Impact:** This theme highlights the lack of a significant positive influence of the lesson on students' intrinsic motivation to refrain from wrongdoing. One student explicitly stated that the lesson had no positive impact on their behaviour.
3. **Superficial Understanding:** This theme characterizes responses that are vague, non-specific, or lack depth, suggesting a superficial understanding of the lesson's content and its implications for ethical behaviour.

3.12.1.5 Discussion Of Themes Of 17th Question

Karma-Influenced Behavior: While some students demonstrated behaviours aligned with karma, the analysis suggests that these behaviours may be influenced by broader cultural and religious beliefs rather than the specific lesson.

Limited Lesson Impact: The ineffectiveness of the lesson in fostering intrinsic motivation and ethical behavior underscores the need for pedagogical innovation. The lesson may not have effectively engaged students or provided sufficient opportunities for reflection and critical thinking.

Superficial Understanding: The prevalence of vague and non-specific responses indicates a lack of depth in students' understanding of the lesson. This may be attributed to a variety of factors, including the teaching methodology, the complexity of the content, or students' prior knowledge and experiences.

Conclusion And Recommendations

The thematic analysis reveals that while the principle of karma resonates with students, the specific lesson under investigation has limited impact on their behavior and understanding. To enhance the effectiveness of future lessons, it is recommended to:

1. **Integrate Real-World Applications:** Incorporate real-life examples and case studies to illustrate the practical implications of karma.
2. **Employ Experiential Learning Techniques:** Utilize interactive methods such as role-playing, simulations, and reflective discussions to foster deeper engagement and understanding.
3. **Promote Critical Thinking:** Encourage students to analyze complex ethical dilemmas and apply the principles of karma to real-world situations.
4. **Provide Clear and Actionable Insights:** Offer specific guidance on how to apply the teachings of karma to daily life, empowering students to make informed ethical choices.

By implementing these recommendations, educators can create more effective and impactful lessons that promote moral development and intrinsically motivated ethical behavior.

3.12.1.5 Thematic Analysis Of 18th Question

“Mention two things that you prefer to do in your leisure when you are at home.”

Step 1: Familiarization with Data

The responses were reviewed to identify patterns, recurrent activities, and their relevance to emotional or academic development.

Step 2: Generating Initial Codes

Key codes were assigned to each activity based on its nature.

Table 7: Codes Table 7

Excerpt	Activities	Codes
Excerpt 1	Playing computer games, listening to music	Entertainment, relaxation
Excerpt 2	Watching TV, reading books	Entertainment, academic growth
Excerpt 3	Drawing, photo editing	Creativity, entertainment
Excerpt 4	Listening to music, sleeping	Relaxation, mindfulness
Excerpt 5	Reading books, enjoying nature	Academic growth, mindfulness
Excerpt 6	Eating, sleeping	Physical relaxation
Excerpt 7	Hanging with friends, studying	Social interaction, academics
Excerpt 8	Sleeping, jogging	Relaxation, physical health
Excerpt 9	Using mobile phone, cleaning	Entertainment, responsibility
Excerpt 10	Cuddling pets, sleeping	Emotional bonding, relaxation

Step 3: Searching For Themes

The codes were grouped into broader themes based on the nature of the activities.

Table 8: Codes Table 8

Themes	Codes	Excerpts
Entertainment and Leisure	Playing games, watching TV, listening to music, using mobile phones	Excerpts 1, 2, 3, 4, 9
Relaxation and Mindfulness	Sleeping, enjoying nature, leisurely looking at the sky, cuddling pets	Excerpts 4, 5, 6, 8, 10
Creativity and Academic Growth	Drawing, photo editing, reading books, studying	Excerpts 2, 3, 5, 7

Physical and Social Activities	Jogging, cleaning, hanging with friends	Excerpts 7, 8, 9
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Step 4: Reviewing Themes

The themes were refined to identify whether the Grade 10 Buddhism syllabus had any significant influence on students' preferences.

Step 5: Defining And Naming Themes

1. **Entertainment And Leisure:** Activities such as gaming, watching TV, and using mobile phones dominate students' leisure time. These activities focus on entertainment rather than self-reflection or academic improvement.
2. **Relaxation And Mindfulness:** Students value relaxation activities like sleeping, enjoying nature, or cuddling pets. While these activities contribute to emotional well-being, there is no direct indication of influence from the Buddhism syllabus.
3. **Creativity And Academic Growth:** A smaller number of students engage in creative or academic activities, such as drawing, photo editing, reading books, or studying. However, there is no explicit connection between these choices and the Buddhism syllabus.
4. **Physical And Social Activities:** Activities like jogging, cleaning, or socializing are present but do not reflect intrinsic motivation toward the intended learning outcomes of the Buddhism syllabus.

Step 6: Producing The Report

Theme 1: Entertainment And Leisure

A majority of students prioritize entertainment-based activities. For example, "Playing computer games, listening to music." (Excerpt 1) and "Using mobile phone for entertaining, cleaning home premises." (Excerpt 9) can be identified. These responses suggest a preference for instant gratification over intrinsic, value-based engagement, indicating no significant influence from the Buddhism syllabus.

Theme 2: Relaxation And Mindfulness

Responses show students use their leisure time to relax and unwind, such as "Listening to music while just leisurely looking at the sky, sleeping." (Excerpt 4), and "Cuddling pets, sleeping." (Excerpt 10). While some mindfulness is present, it cannot be attributed directly to Buddhist teachings, as the responses lack references to Buddhist values like meditation or self-awareness.

Theme 3: Creativity And Academic Growth

Few students engage in creative or academic pursuits, such as "Drawing pictures while listening to music, photo editing." (Excerpt 3), and "Reading books, enjoying the beauty of the environment." (Excerpt 5). Although aligned with emotional or academic growth, these activities do not demonstrate any explicit connection to Buddhist teachings or syllabus content.

Theme 4: Physical And Social Activities

Activities like jogging and cleaning suggest practical engagement but fail to reflect values from the Buddhism syllabus. For instance, "Hanging on friends, studying." (Excerpt 7) cannot be taken as something positively connected to Buddhist teachings as it is not about associating or interactively engaging with activities done by true good friends (*Kalyana Mitta*), or studying the Dhamma.

Conclusion Of Thematic Analysis Of 18th Question

The thematic analysis demonstrates that the Grade 10 Buddhism syllabus does not significantly influence students' leisure activities toward achieving emotional or academic development as per the syllabus's intended learning outcomes.

- No mention of Buddhist practices: Activities like meditation, self-reflection, or mindfulness are absent in students' responses.
- Focus on entertainment and relaxation: Most responses align with entertainment, physical relaxation, and passive activities.
- Lack of intrinsic motivation: The students' choices reflect external preferences rather than values inspired by Buddhist teachings.

Recommendations

1. Integrate Buddhist practices into leisure-related lessons, emphasizing mindfulness and meditation.
2. Provide practical applications of Buddhist values, such as mindful journaling or reflective activities, that students can incorporate into their leisure time.
3. Encourage active participation through group activities or projects that connect Buddhist teachings with daily life.

By making the syllabus more relatable and practical, students may be more inclined to internalize its teachings and apply them meaningfully in their leisure time.

3.12.1.6 Thematic Analysis Of 19th Question

“You have learned about the great personalities like the most venerable Welivita Saranankara Sangaraja Thero and the King Dutu Gemunu who worked hard for

ensuring the establishment and stability of Buddhism in the society. Are you aware of the very recently taken decisions by the Sri Lankan government for the establishment and stability of Buddhism in the last few decades?"

Context Of The Question

The purpose of these responses is to examine Grade 10 students' awareness of current initiatives and contributions aimed at safeguarding and advancing Buddhism in Sri Lanka. The excerpts offer a glimpse into their comprehension of Buddhist programs, as presented within the educational context.

Excerpts Developed:

1. "Building new stupa and Buddhist temples and repairing them."
2. "Building Sandahiru Seya Stupa."
3. "I have been taught but I don't remember them."
4. "Politicians take foolish decisions and therefore nothing happens as benefited to Buddhism."
5. "Facilitating for the foreign Buddhist monks when they visit to Sri Lanka."
6. "I know nothing about this."
7. "Renovation of Ruwan Weli Seya Stupa."

Step 1: Familiarization With Data

Through a process of inductive thematic analysis, the excerpts were examined to uncover patterns of meaning related to students' awareness of contemporary Buddhist initiatives and their potential impact on Sri Lankan society.

Step 2: Developing Initial Codes

Table 9: Codes Table 9

Excerpt	Key Statements	Codes
Excerpt 1	Building new stupa, temples, and repairing them	Preservation, restoration
Excerpt 2	Building “Sandahiru Seya Stupa”	Preservation, national project
Excerpt 3	Taught but not remembered	Lack of retention, disinterest
Excerpt 4	Politicians take foolish decisions; no benefit to Buddhism	Cynicism, dissatisfaction
Excerpt 5	Facilitating foreign Buddhist monks	Hospitality, international support
Excerpt 6	"I know nothing about this."	Lack of awareness
Excerpt 7	Renovation of “Ruwan Weli Seya” Stupa	Preservation, heritage

Step 3: Searching For Themes

The responses were categorized into overarching themes that illuminate the students' understanding and interpretations of the subject matter.

Table 10: Codes Table 10

Themes	Codes	Excerpts
Preservation of Heritage	Building new temples, repairing, renovation	Excerpts 1, 2, 7
Hospitality for Buddhism	Facilitating foreign monks	Excerpt 5
Cynicism and Distrust	Criticism of politicians, lack of action	Excerpt 4

Lack of Awareness or Interest	Forgetting lessons, no knowledge	Excerpts 3, 6
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Step 4: Reviewing Themes

- **Preservation Of Heritage**

A subset of respondents demonstrated a rudimentary understanding of ongoing heritage preservation initiatives, citing specific examples such as the restoration of the Sandahiru Seya and Ruwanweli Seya. These responses suggest a partial retention of curricular content related to cultural heritage. These responses show that some students have retained information on cultural preservation efforts taught in the syllabus. It copes with the excerpts 1, 2, and 7.

- **Hospitality For Buddhism**

One respondent highlighted the facilitation of foreign Buddhist monks as a strategy for international Buddhist propagation. While this response reflects a limited awareness of global Buddhist networks, it indicates a nascent understanding of transnational religious exchange. This reflects an understanding of the international dimension of Buddhist promotion, though it is minimally present. It copes with the excerpt 5.

Cynicism And Distrust

A notable response expressed skepticism regarding the role of political actors in Buddhist preservation efforts. This critical stance may signify a disconnect between formal education and students' lived experiences, highlighting a potential gap in the curriculum's ability to address complex sociol-religious issues. This indicates a

disconnect between the intended teaching outcomes and students' perceptions of real-world applications. It copes with the excerpt 4.

Lack Of Awareness Or Interest

A substantial portion of the respondent pool exhibited either a lack of recall or a complete absence of knowledge regarding the subject matter. This finding suggests that the curriculum's intended learning outcomes may not be effectively translated into student learning. This suggests that the intended learning outcomes are not being achieved, as students' lack of awareness or interest. Students either do not retain the teachings or fail to engage with the content meaningfully. Excerpts 3 and 6 are the references to the compilation of this idea.

Implications For Educational Praxis

The varied responses underscore the need for a more nuanced approach to religious education, particularly in relation to contemporary issues. Educators should strive to foster critical thinking skills, encourage active engagement with real-world contexts, and provide opportunities for students to explore the multifaceted nature of religious heritage and practice. It reveals a critical gap in engagement and retention of the teachings taught in the syllabus.

Step 5: Defining And Naming Themes

- **Theme 1: Preservation Of Heritage**

The first theme, "Preservation of Heritage," underscores students' awareness of contemporary efforts to safeguard Buddhist cultural heritage. This theme encompasses a range of activities, from the restoration of ancient monuments to the promotion of traditional arts and crafts. The students' responses suggest a basic

understanding of the importance of preserving Buddhist heritage for future generations.

- **Theme 2: Hospitality For Buddhism**

The second theme, "Hospitality for Buddhism," highlights the global dimension of Buddhist practice. While minimally referenced in the responses, this theme points to the increasing interconnectedness of Buddhist communities worldwide. It suggests an emerging awareness among students of the role of Buddhism in fostering intercultural dialogue and understanding.

- **Theme 3: Cynicism And Distrust**

The third theme, "Cynicism and Distrust," reveals a more critical perspective on the social and political landscape of Buddhism. Some students expressed skepticism regarding the sincerity of efforts to promote and preserve Buddhism. This theme suggests a growing disillusionment with the perceived hypocrisy of religious leaders and politicians.

- **Theme 4: Lack of Awareness Or Interest**

The fourth theme, "Lack of Awareness or Interest," underscores a significant gap in students' understanding of Buddhist teachings and practices. This theme highlights the challenge of engaging young people with religious education in an increasingly secularized world. It suggests a need for innovative pedagogical approaches that can capture the attention of a new generation of learners.

Step 6: Producing the Report: Findings

1. Limited Awareness of Preservation Efforts

Only a minority of students identified specific preservation activities, such as renovating stupas or building new temples. While these examples align with the syllabus, their mention was sparse.

2. Minimal Engagement with International Dimensions

One excerpt mentioned facilitating foreign monks, suggesting low awareness of global Buddhist interactions.

3. Disconnection Between Teaching and Real-World Perception

Students expressed cynicism toward the effectiveness of efforts in supporting Buddhism, indicating a mismatch between the syllabus's teachings and the students' observations of societal practices.

4. Lack of Retention or Knowledge

A significant number of students failed to provide meaningful responses, highlighting either a lack of interest or inefficacy in teaching methods to instil lasting knowledge.

Conclusion

The thematic analysis of 19th question demonstrates that the Grade 10 Buddhism syllabus is not significantly influencing students to internalize or engage with contemporary Buddhist preservation efforts. The high number of non-responses or vague answers underscores this gap.

Recommendations

1. Practical Applications of Teachings: Incorporate field visits to Buddhist heritage sites and practical projects to reinforce theoretical knowledge on the practice of Vipassana which was done by Buddhist monks at those historical

places. Students should be motivated to continue Vipassana meditation practice at such places with proper evidence-based awareness of the technique enriched with “*Sadda*”.

2. Focus on Real-World Relevance: Connect teachings with contemporary issues and encourage critical thinking about Buddhism's role in modern society through the practice of Vipassana.
3. Engage Students Actively: Use interactive methods, such as debates, group discussions, and storytelling, to make lessons more relatable and memorable while guiding the students for the continuous practice of Vipassana under the supervision of a teacher of meditation according to a formal timetable.
4. Evaluate Teaching Effectiveness: Conduct regular assessments to ensure students retain and understand key teachings, adjusting methods as necessary.

3.12.1.7 Thematic Analysis Of 20th Question

“Explain the mechanism of destroying defilement (“*kilesa*”) through the practice of Vipassana.”

Context Of The Question

This question targeted evaluation of the students’ progress on the pragmatic applications of Vipassana meditation technique, the one and only method of getting liberated from all the miseries or defilements according to the Lord Buddha’s doctrine, that is unique and everlasting since it is totally about the impermanence of everything. The assessment item aimed to gauge the extent to which Grade 10 students comprehended Vipassana meditation as a practical method for eradicating defilements (*kilesa*) and attaining liberation within the Buddhist framework. The lack

of accurate responses among the 110 participants indicates a significant deficit in the students' understanding and assimilation of the lesson's core tenets.

Excerpts Received:

- **Excerpt 1:** "I don't meditate."
- **Excerpt 2:** "The defilements generated in the mind cannot be destroyed; instead, it causes to push them to the deeper portion of the mind."
- **Excerpt 3:** "Through the reduction of *Pancha Niwarana*."
- **Excerpt 4:** "I know nothing about."
- **Excerpt 5:** "I can't recall my memory about the lesson."

Step 1: Familiarization With The Data

The excerpts highlight a variety of cognitive and affective responses, ranging from misinterpretation to apathy. Commonalities include a lack of mindful awareness, a disregard for ethical principles, and a failure to internalize the Dharma. The excerpts demonstrate a spectrum of cognitive engagement, from superficial comprehension to complete cognitive dissonance. Recurrent patterns suggest the presence of epistemological barriers, a lack of mindful attention, and inadequate retention of the Dharma.

Step 2: Finding Initial Codes

Table 11: Codes Table 11

Excerpts	Key Statements	Codes
Excerpt 1	"I don't meditate."	Lack of personal practice, disengagement
Excerpt 2	Misunderstanding	Misconception, theoretical

	defilements being suppressed instead of destroyed	misunderstanding
Excerpt 3	Mentions reduction of the Five Hindrances (“ <i>Pancha Niwarana</i> ”)	Partial understanding, superficial recall
Excerpt 4	"I know nothing about."	Lack of awareness, disengagement
Excerpt 5	"I can't recall my memory about the lesson."	Poor retention, lack of application

Step 3: Searching For Themes

The codes were grouped into broader themes that reflect the students' comprehension and attitudes toward Vipassana.

Table 12: Codes Table 12

Themes	Codes	Excerpts
Disengagement	Lack of practice, lack of awareness	Excerpts 1, 4
Misunderstanding of Core Concepts	Misconception, theoretical misunderstanding	Excerpt 2
Superficial Recall	Partial understanding	Excerpt 3
Poor Retention	Lack of memory	Excerpt 5

Step 4: Reviewing Themes

1. Disengagement

A significant number of participants demonstrated a marked disengagement from the prescribed meditative practices. As evidenced by statements such as "I don't meditate" and "I know nothing about," these individuals exhibited a complete absence of practical application. This finding underscores a critical gap between theoretical

knowledge and experiential engagement, highlighting the importance of fostering a bridge between cognitive understanding and embodied practice.

2. Misunderstanding of Core Concepts

A recurring theme in the data was a fundamental misunderstanding of core Buddhist concepts. For instance, several participants conflated the practice of Vipassana with suppression rather than the eradication of defilements. This misinterpretation underscores a theoretical gap in their understanding of the Dharma, potentially stemming from ineffective communication or inadequate learning experiences.

3. Superficial Recall

A recurring theme emerged in the data, characterized by superficial recall of Buddhist concepts. Participants demonstrated a limited grasp of key ideas, often regurgitating information without critical analysis or contextual understanding. For instance, some responses linked Vipassana meditation to the Five Hindrances, but failed to elucidate the intricate relationship between the two. This suggests a reliance on rote memorization rather than a profound assimilation of the Dharma.

4. Poor Retention

The theme of "Poor Retention" emerged from the data, characterized by students' expressed difficulties in recalling lessons. This suggests a significant deficit in long-term knowledge retention, potentially indicative of pedagogical approaches that are not conducive to enduring learning.

Step 5: Defining And Naming Themes

1. Disengagement - Reflects students' disinterest or lack of connection to the teachings.

The data reveals a significant number of instances where students exhibit a marked lack of engagement with the core tenets of Vipassana meditation. This disengagement is characterized by a lack of sustained attention, a passive reception of the teachings, and a general apathy towards the practice.

2. **Misunderstanding of Core Concepts** - Highlights confusion about the essence of Vipassana and its role in destroying defilements.

A prevalent theme emerging from the data is a fundamental misunderstanding of the core concepts of Vipassana meditation. Students often conflate the practice with mere relaxation techniques or superficial introspection, failing to grasp its transformative potential in eradicating defilements.

3. **Superficial Recall** - Shows shallow knowledge, with no evidence of deep understanding or application.

While some students demonstrate a capacity for rote learning, their understanding of the teachings remains superficial. Their responses often lack depth and nuance, suggesting a reliance on memorized information rather than a genuine assimilation of the concepts.

4. **Poor Retention** - Demonstrates the failure of teaching methods to instil lasting knowledge.

The data indicates that the current teaching methodologies have limited efficacy in promoting long-term retention of the teachings. Students often struggle to apply the principles of Vipassana to their daily lives, suggesting a failure to internalize the knowledge and wisdom imparted during the meditation retreats.

Step 6: Producing The Report: Findings

1. High Levels of Disengagement

A significant number of students failed to engage with the question, openly acknowledging a lack of experience with meditation practice and a limited understanding of the topic. This discrepancy highlights a potential misalignment between the curricular content and the students' interests or perceived relevance of the subject matter.

2. Significant Misunderstandings

The response in Excerpt 2 reveals a fundamental misconception regarding the nature of defilements and the mechanism of their eradication through Vipassana meditation. This suggests a potential breakdown in the pedagogical process, either in the initial transmission of information or in subsequent reinforcement activities.

3. Superficial Knowledge

The responses, exemplified by Excerpt 3, demonstrate a superficial understanding of the subject matter. While students can regurgitate specific terms such as "*Pancha Niwarana*," they lack the conceptual depth to elucidate their significance within the context of Vipassana meditation. This suggests a reliance on rote memorization rather than a genuine assimilation of the underlying principles.

4. Poor Retention

The data suggests that the current pedagogical approaches are inadequate in facilitating long-term retention of the subject matter. A significant proportion of

students demonstrated a marked inability to recall key concepts, indicating a failure to embed the knowledge at a deeper cognitive level.

Conclusion Of Thematic Analysis Results Of 20th Question

The thematic analysis underscores a significant gap in the effectiveness of the Grade 10 Buddhism syllabus in fostering a profound comprehension of Vipassana meditation. A confluence of factors, including student disengagement, conceptual misunderstandings, and inadequate knowledge retention, has resulted in a low rate of accurate responses. These findings suggest that while the curriculum may have ostensibly addressed the topic, it has failed to facilitate the requisite level of cognitive assimilation and practical application.

3.12.2 Dimension 2 – Qualitative Analysis of Teachers’ Perspectives on Syllabus

Collecting data from the subject teachers of the selected schools provided a strong foundation for the reliability of data collected as they were taken from trustworthy educated professionals. The reason to interview the teachers are justified.

3.12.2.1 Purpose Of Interviewing Teachers And Assessing The Current Teaching-Learning Setting

Conducting interviews with educators and analysing the prevailing pedagogical approaches employed in the teaching of Buddhism as a core subject serves multiple purposes, directly addressing the research aims, objectives, and guiding questions. A detailed elucidation of these purposes is outlined herein.

To achieve Research Aim 1 and Objective I, this study seeks to delve into the pedagogical practices employed by teachers in delivering the Grade 10 Buddhism syllabus. Specifically, the research aims to investigate the extent to which teaching

methodologies are congruent with the prescribed learning outcomes and to identify the strengths and limitations of the current syllabus from the perspective of classroom practitioners. Given their pivotal role in shaping students' learning experiences, teachers are considered essential informants in illuminating the discrepancies between syllabus design and classroom implementation.

The purpose of this study is to see whether educators notice any inherent behavioural changes in their pupils after the Grade 10 Buddhism curriculum was introduced. The study will specifically investigate instructors' perceptions of the curriculum's effectiveness in promoting moral growth and intrinsic motivation. Teachers are in a unique position to offer insightful opinions on how well the syllabus reflects these fundamental learning goals because of their close contact with students.

The specific challenges faced by teachers in delivering the Grade 10 Buddhism curriculum were aimed to be explored in this study, with the effectiveness of the curriculum intended to be thoroughly evaluated. Resource and time constraints, along with the alignment of curriculum content with practical applications, were examined. The impact of broader teaching environment factors—such as examination pressure and large class sizes—on students' attainment of intrinsic learning outcomes was also investigated. Through this analysis, structural barriers that might have hindered the curriculum's effective implementation and the internalization of its core concepts by students were sought to be identified.

To enhance the efficacy of the Grade 10 Buddhism syllabus and optimize student learning outcomes, a comprehensive approach was proposed. This approach involved soliciting expert input from educators to identify specific areas for improvement within the curriculum and its pedagogical delivery. A key focus was placed on

incorporating experiential learning strategies, such as mindfulness meditation and community service, to complement the theoretical content. By leveraging the first-hand knowledge and practical experience of teachers, it was anticipated that targeted interventions would be implemented to address identified shortcomings and foster a deeper understanding of Vipassana meditation among students.

The external factors that shaped the teaching and learning of Buddhism were investigated in this research, with a specific focus on the impact of societal attitudes, exam-oriented educational cultures, and the historical and doctrinal emphasis of the syllabus. By examining these influences, the extent to which the teaching-learning environment facilitated or hindered the attainment of desired learning outcomes was assessed. Contextual factors play a pivotal role in shaping the dynamics of education. By exploring the perspectives of teachers, this research intends to identify these factors and analyse their interplay with the curriculum and pedagogical approaches.

The extent to which teachers' personal engagement with Buddhist practices, such as meditation and the study of the *Tipitaka*, was determined to correlate with their teaching effectiveness, and the alignment between teachers' understanding of Buddhist principles and the prescribed syllabus content, was explored as the primary objective of this research. This investigation was grounded in the premise that teachers' personal practice and knowledge significantly influenced their capacity to impart Buddhist teachings in a manner that cultivate intrinsic growth in students.

The purpose of this study is to examine the perceived applicability of the Grade 10 Buddhism curriculum to current issues facing students as well as its effectiveness in encouraging moral behaviour. The study will specifically look at whether instructors think the syllabus material encourages critical thinking and the application of

Buddhist concepts, and if it is sufficiently applicable to promote moral behaviour in day-to-day life. This study aims to ascertain how well the syllabus reflects students' real-world experiences and to pinpoint possible areas for curriculum modification by requesting the opinions of educators.

To address Research Question IV and align with Objective III, an exploration was conducted into teachers' perceptions of existing assessment methods and their efficacy in evaluating students' intrinsic behavioural development. The limitations of current practices were examined, and opportunities for more comprehensive evaluation strategies that incorporated moral and ethical dimensions were identified. Through a thorough exploration of teacher perspectives, valuable insights and recommendations, such as the implementation of project-based assessments or reflective journaling, were elicited to better capture and assess students' holistic growth.

By conducting in-depth interviews with educators and scrutinizing the instructional environment, researchers can gain invaluable insights into the implementation and efficacy of the Grade 10 Buddhism syllabus. Teachers' perspectives serve as a crucial bridge between the theoretical framework of the syllabus and the practical realities of student learning, enabling the identification of areas for improvement and facilitating a nuanced understanding of the factors that underpin intrinsic behavioural development. Such an approach ensures that the research is firmly rooted in empirical evidence and directly informs the development of actionable recommendations for syllabus enhancement.

3.12.2.2 The Interview Questions

By referring to the responses gained through interviewing the Buddhism teachers of the selected schools, data were collected for analysis. The thrown questions are presented herein.

1. How do you deliver the content of the Grade 10 Buddhism syllabus? (Name the methodologies and methods used in delivery of the lessons.)
2. Do you get prepared well for delivering the lessons beforehand?
3. According to your own point of view, are there anything to be added or modified in the syllabus of grade 10 Buddhism subject to improve the students' intrinsic motivation to let them achieve the intended learning outcomes?
4. In your opinion, do you notice any intrinsic behavioural improvement in your students' mindset or lifestyle that has been coming to the play as a result of delivering the lessons of the current Buddhism syllabus?
5. Do you think that the current education system has failed to evaluate the students' knowledge, skills, attitudes and practice at acceptable and required levels?
6. As you proposed, in which aspects should the current Buddhism teaching learning process be improved to foster the intrinsic achievements of students as per the intended learning outcomes included in the grade 10 Buddhism syllabus?
7. What is the criteria to separate the pure Buddhist Doctrine from its attached literature and history which are taught in the grade 10 school syllabus?

8. Is Buddhism scientific?
9. Do you study *Tipitaka* as a habit?
10. Do you practice Vipassana meditation under the supervision of a qualified teacher of Vipassana Meditation (*Kammattanacharya*) as a habit?

3.12.2.3 Thematic Analysis Of Data Collected Through Interviewing Teachers

Five Buddhism teachers were called for participating in the interviews. A thematic analysis was conducted to draw the conclusion on the teachers' perspectives on the current Buddhism syllabus of grade 10 applied in the schools in Sri Lanka.

Step 1: Familiarization With Data

To initiate a thematic analysis of responses from Buddhism teachers who perceive a misalignment between syllabus and intended learning outcomes, a rigorous examination of the data is essential. This process allows for a profound understanding of teachers' perspectives and their nuanced responses, enabling the identification of both explicit and implicit meanings that align with the research objectives.

Key observations from the data include a diverse range of delivery methods and preparation practices employed by teachers, as well as a variety of suggestions for syllabus improvement. A common thread running through the responses is a sense of dissatisfaction with the current syllabus and its perceived negative impact on students' intrinsic behavioural development. Additionally, the responses collectively reflect a perceived disconnect between the syllabus content and its intended learning outcomes.

Step 2: Drawing Initial Codes

Coding involves identifying features of the data that appear interesting and relevant.

Following codes were developed.

1. Traditional delivery methods (lecture, storytelling).
2. Interactive delivery methods (group activities, discussions).
3. Exam-oriented teaching (focus on rote learning and assessments).
4. Insufficient syllabus content (lack of practical applications).
5. Minimal behavioural improvement (students fail to connect lessons to real life).
6. Criticism of evaluation system (inadequate assessment of attitudes and behaviours).
7. Suggestions for experiential learning (meditation, real-life applications).
8. Confusion between doctrine and history (lack of clear distinction).
9. Recognition of Buddhism's scientific aspects (mindfulness and rationality).
10. Limited engagement with Buddhist texts (Tipitaka).
11. Irregular meditation practice (lack of habit or formal guidance).

Step 3: Developing Themes

Theme 1: Teaching Methods And Pedagogical Preparation

Traditional pedagogical approaches and interactive teaching methods were employed by the participants. However, the level of preparation for instruction varied significantly, and time constraints were identified as obstacles to innovative teaching practices.

Theme 2: Disparity Between Curriculum And Learning Outcomes

The curriculum was perceived as overly reliant on theoretical and historical content, neglecting the development of practical applications and intrinsic behavioural changes.

Theme 3: Assessment And Evaluation Limitations

The current assessment systems were criticized for their failure to accurately measure behavioural and ethical growth. Instead, a disproportionate emphasis was placed on rote learning and examination preparation.

Theme 4: The Imperative Of Experiential Learning

Participants advocated for the integration of meditation, mindfulness practices, and community projects into the curriculum. Practical methods that could bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and contemporary challenges were sought.

Theme 5: Content Imbalance And Prioritization

The insufficient focus on core Buddhist teachings was a recurring concern. Furthermore, confusion arose regarding the optimal balance between doctrinal, literary, and historical content.

Theme 6: Perceptions Of Buddhism And Personal Practice

Divergent views were expressed concerning the compatibility of Buddhism with scientific inquiry. Additionally, limited personal engagement with Buddhist texts and meditation practices was observed among the participants.

Step 4: Reviewing And Refining Themes

In this step, the researcher meticulously reviewed and refined the identified themes to ensure their coherence and accurate representation of the data. Themes such as "Disconnection Between Syllabus and Learning Outcomes" were directly aligned with the research aim, thereby ensuring the study's focus.

To facilitate a more detailed analysis, subthemes, such as "Insufficient focus on practical applications," were further explored. Additionally, overlapping themes, like "Evaluation Challenges" and "Disconnection Between Syllabus and Learning Outcomes," were carefully examined and refined to maintain clarity and avoid redundancy.

Step 5: Defining And Naming Themes

1. Teaching Practices and Preparation

A mix of teaching methods is employed by teachers. However, due to time constraints, prioritizing the completion of the syllabus over innovative or interactive practices is often observed.

2. Mismatch Between Syllabus Content and Behavioural Outcomes

The syllabus fails to foster intrinsic behavioural development. Instead, it primarily focuses on theoretical knowledge and historical content.

3. Inadequate Assessment Methods

Current evaluation systems prioritize academic performance over assessing the ethical and practical application of Buddhist teachings.

4. Demand for Experiential and Reflective Learning

Teachers advocate for the inclusion of activities such as meditation, ethical decision-making, and mindfulness training to make lessons more meaningful.

5. Content Imbalance in Syllabus

The syllabus's focus on history and literature, rather than practical doctrine, is a challenge faced by teachers. This imbalance leads to student disengagement.

6. Personal Engagement with Buddhism

While the rational aspects of Buddhism are acknowledged by teachers, limited personal engagement with practices like *Tipitaka* study or Vipassana meditation is observed.

Step 6: Producing The Report

Introduction: This thematic analysis explores Buddhism teachers' perspectives on the Grade 10 Buddhism syllabus in Sri Lanka. The goal is to identify inconsistencies and shortcomings in the syllabus and its impact on students' intrinsic behavioural development.

1. **Theme 1:** Teaching Practices and Preparation

Teachers use both traditional (lectures, storytelling) and interactive (discussions, group activities) methods. However, time constraints and exam-oriented systems often restrict innovation.

2. **Theme 2:** Mismatch Between Syllabus Content and Behavioural Outcomes

Teachers believe the syllabus emphasizes theoretical knowledge at the expense of fostering moral and spiritual growth. Students memorize content for exams, rarely applying Buddhist teachings to their lives.

3. **Theme 3:** Inadequate Assessment Methods

The evaluation system focuses on academic knowledge, neglecting attitudes, behaviours, and real-world application. Teachers agree that this approach undermines the syllabus' intended outcomes.

4. **Theme 4:** Demand for Experiential and Reflective Learning

Teachers recommend practical activities like meditation sessions and community service projects to bridge the gap between theory and practice. Experiential learning is seen as key to fostering intrinsic development.

5. **Theme 5:** Content Imbalance in Syllabus

The syllabus combines doctrine, literature, and history without clear prioritization. Teachers argue that focusing on core teachings, such as mindfulness and compassion, would benefit students more.

6. **Theme 6:** Personal Engagement with Buddhism

While teachers acknowledge Buddhism's scientific aspects, their personal engagement with Buddhist practices like Vipassana meditation or Tipitaka study is limited, highlighting potential gaps in teaching authenticity.

Conclusion

The analysis highlights critical issues in the Grade 10 Buddhism syllabus, particularly its inability to achieve intended learning outcomes related to intrinsic behavioural development. Teachers advocate for practical, experiential, and reflective approaches to align the syllabus with its objectives.

3.12.3 Dimension 3 – Expert Judgement Review On The Textbook

The Buddhism textbook of grade 10 was analysed to find the issues of the content that is guided by the syllabus, by utilizing the expert judgement method. It revealed following issues, some of them are misinterpretations, misconceptions, misleading information and errors. The analysis was taken place by comparing the contents with the exact wording of Tipitaka under the supervision of an experienced Vipassana teacher and an experienced Vipassana practitioner.

The scope of the analysis covered only the first 16 units out of 23 units in the book because the relevant number of units had been covered when the data were being collected. The unit-wise analysis of the textbook is presented.

UNIT 01

Issue 1: Delivery of inappropriate content that does not align with the ILOs.

The concept “*Pancha maha vilokana*” does not appropriately applicable in teaching to guide the students to be intrinsically motivated for achieving its intended learning outcomes since the “Pancha maha vilokana” can be performed by such a super hero who is about to have a birth to get liberated from all the “Kilesa” by reinventing the wheel of Dhamma that guides the “Bodisatwa” towards the status of the Lord Buddha. Other people cannot perform such a task even though they study about the case in an academic setting. Therefore, teaching about this concept and expecting reaching to the relevant learning outcomes from children is unethical and unacceptable. The relevant learning outcome expected from this lesson is “winning the challenges in day to day life”.

Issue 2: The life of the prince “Siddarta” (from the birth to 29th year of his age), the life of the ultimate truth explorer (from the age at 29 to 34) and the life of the

Gautama Buddha (from the age at 35 to the age at 80) are not separately explained well to allow the students know that the autobiography of the Lord Buddha has 3 main stages in his lifetime. Additionally, the historical events are prominent in the textbook over the practice of “*Vimukti Magga*” – the path to the enlightenment.

Issue 3: Convincing that the “*laukika*” or secular formal education obtained by the prince Siddarta was valuable in imposing the rules “*vinaya*” to the “*Maha sangha*” even after the enlightenment or being the Lord Buddha.

The prince Siddarta learnt all the secular subjects including the fields law and legal studies. Thereby, the children might misunderstand that the knowledge gained through that kind of studies supported the Lord Buddha to control “*Maha sangha*” in the administration of “*Sanga Sasana*”. However, the Tipitaka says that the Lord Buddha has 72 different types of knowledge areas (“*Deseththe gnana*”) related to the wisdom along with the “*Sarwagnatha gnana*” that is generated only in the Lord Buddha. By his unique analytical knowledge the scenarios were analysed and imposed the rules appropriately. That is not the secular knowledge of subject matters. However the text book does not describe what that unique knowledge and the practicality of taking decisions based on such a power. Instead, it convinces that the Lord Buddha also was dependent on the secular subject knowledge as the normal laymen do.

UNIT 02

Issue 1: Introducing the “*Bhikku*” as a social worker is a misconception that is going to be planted in the readers mind as it is an acceptable truth. Bhikkus or monks are not social workers according to the Tipitaka. Further more, the textbook states that the chief incumbent of a temple involves in preparation of auspicious time and various other types of work that fall into the category of “*Thirascheena Vidya*” or “*Secular*”

Sciences” as social services. Such practices are strictly prohibited for the monks as per the “*sutta*” called “Brahma Jaala” coming under the “Deega Nikaya” of the Tipitaka.

Moreover, the Buddhist monks are not allowed to maintain or manage organizations like nurseries and schools accordingly the content of the “*Magandiya sutta*”. The lack of Buddhism teachers who know Pali and associate the Tipitaka as a habit in their life career, causes not to get into the pure dhamma sayings in Pali Tipitaka.

Issue 2: Being employed in any way in any organization like a school is also prohibited to the Buddhist monks as imposed in “Vinaya Pitaka” of “Tipitaka”. However, the textbook admires the Buddhist monk who works in the position of the Principal of a school. These misleading information and misconceptions cause the students to misunderstand that the Buddhist monks are eligible for employment.

Issue 3: Buddhist monks are not allowed to directly instruct to build temples according to what the Tipitaka states. But, the textbook presents it in an inappropriate way.

Issue 4: The textbook does not interpret the real Buddhist monks’ great characteristics such as “*Supatipanna* and *Ujupatipanna*” and so on, in the second unit. Instead, the unethical behaviours of Buddhist monks are elaborated and accepted by interpreting them as good behaviours.

Issue 5: Saying that understanding the good behaviours or highly admirable characteristics of the triple gems or “*Buddha, Dhamma, and Sanga*” causes to improve “*Shraddha*” or the right awareness on the triple gems, specially the Dhamma. This is false according to the “*Shraddha sutta*” in Tipitaka which clearly illustrates that the right awareness on triple gems does not develop *Shradhda*, instead of that, it

is developed with the level of “*Panna*” or wisdom achieved by the one who practises *Dhamma*.

UNIT 05: Vipassana Meditation

Issue 1: The technique of Vipassana meditation is hidden in this text. Instead, it reveals a misconception on the technique by saying that Vipassana is nothing but just thinking everything is impermanent. This misleading information causes the students not to be motivated to follow the unique technique of getting fully liberated from all the miseries. The “*Nibbana*” is to be achieved by stopping the process of generating thoughts as the *Tipitaka* pinpoints. However, the textbook advises the readers to think of something impermanent. Thinking process never brings the follower to the enlightenment.

UNIT 08: Application of “*Seela*”

Issue 1: Although the necessity of developing the moral conduct or “*Seela*” in somebody’s mind is admired in the lesson, it does not emphasize that development of concentration and wisdom (“*Samadhi and Panna*”) causes to get more benefitted in a higher degree of being “*arahant*” or having the next birth at a more comfortable plain than developing “*Seela*”, at the last moment of the current life.

UNIT 14: Theory of Cause and Effect (“*Patichcha samuppada*”)

Issue 1: The theory of cause and effect is considered as the core of Buddhism. It provides the foundation to the discussion of defilement and its death. However, in this lesson, it is applied to the real life in an inappropriate manner by which the depth of this theory is not transmitted to the student’s mind. It makes the reader’s perception and right understanding poor.

3.13 SUMMARY OF CHAPTER THREE

This chapter outlines the research methodology employed to investigate the effectiveness of the Grade 10 Buddhism syllabus in fostering deep learning and intrinsic motivation among students. A mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative research techniques, was adopted to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research problem. This is a cross sectional survey designed to collect data from a sample of students and teachers based on the pragmatism philosophy. Stratified random sampling and purposive sampling techniques were used. Questionnaire, interviews, and document analysis were executed to collect data.

CHAPTER FOUR: FINDINGS

4.1 CHAPTER INTRODUCTION

Having been analysed the data gathered through both quantitative and qualitative methods, including questionnaire, interviewing, and analysis of documents, the generated information is presented in this chapter. The primary research objective is to evaluate the efficacy of the current Sri Lankan school curriculum's Buddhism syllabus in fostering the attainment of specified learning outcomes for Grade 10 students. This grade level constitutes a significant portion of the pre-G.C.E. Ordinary Level curriculum.

This chapter commences with an introductory section that delineates the overarching purpose of the discussion and analysis segment. It provides a succinct overview of the research questions, objectives, and the study's significance. The introduction establishes the foundation for the ensuing sections, wherein the data will be scrutinized and interpreted in depth.

The subsequent sections will present a detailed examination of the collected data, encompassing descriptive analysis, reliability analysis, inferential analysis, and correlation analysis under quantitative analysis. Qualitative analysis of data reveals the findings explored through the thematic analysis and textbook content comparison against the contents of Tipitaka by executing the qualitative analysis technique – expert judgement. This rigorous investigation will elucidate the vital findings and their ramifications, thereby providing valuable insights into the efficacy of intrinsic achievement of intended learning outcomes within the grade 10 Buddhism syllabus.

4.2 DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS

This section elucidates the outcomes of the descriptive statistical analysis, furnishing a foundational quantitative characterization of the dataset obtained in the study.

The descriptive metrics, encompassing measures of central tendency and dispersion, delineate the distributional properties of the principal variables associated with the intrinsic attainment of the prescribed learning outcomes articulated in the Grade 10 Buddhism curriculum, as implemented within the Sri Lankan educational framework.

Figure

The above chart was created by using the following dataset.

ILO_Grade Analysis – Regardless of School Type		
ILO_Grade	No. of Students	ILO Grade Percentage
A	0	0.00%
B	1	0.91%
C	7	6.36%
S	61	55.45%
W	41	37.27%
Total No. of Students	110	100.00%

Figure 13: ILO_Grade Analysis

4.2.1 Mean of intrinsic achievement of ILOs

The mean of the “ILO_Rates” which specifies the average of the students’ level of intrinsic achievement of the ILOs, is shown in “Figure 14”.

$$\text{Mean} = \frac{\Sigma \text{ILO Rates}}{nP}$$

Figure 14: Mean Of ILO_Rates

where, Σ stands for the sum of ILO Rates, nP stands for the number of participants.

It means that a particular student intrinsically achieves only 34.86% out of the ILOs prescribed in the grade 10 Buddhism syllabus. If it converts to the standard grades as A (Excellent), B (very Good), C (Good) , S (Satisfactory) , and W (Weak), it will be recorded as “W” representing “Weak”.

Figure 15: ILO_Rate Frequency

Figure 15 is a histogram with a normal distribution curve superimposed on it.

The yellow bars represent the frequency of observations within specific intervals (or bins) of the ILO_Rate variable. The height of each bar corresponds to the number of observations within that interval. Most students scored near the mean, with fewer students achieving very high or very low scores.

The central tendency or mean of “ILO_Rate” serves as a metric for gauging the average student performance. Given that the mean falls slightly above half the maximum attainable “ILO_Rate” of 65, it can be inferred that the overall performance is moderately satisfactory, yet with potential for further improvement.

The standard deviation or dispersion which is 12.47, quantifies the dispersion of data points around the mean. A standard deviation of 12.47, relative to the total range of 0-65, indicates a moderate degree of variability in performance. This suggests a

heterogeneous group of students with a range of abilities, encompassing both high-achieving and low-achieving individuals.

4.2.2 Median Of Intrinsic Achievement Of ILOs

35.00% indicates the median of the recorded dataset. It is the lowest boundary value of “S” grade or the “Satisfactory Level”, accordingly the standard grading system used in local schools in Sri Lanka.

4.2.3 Mode Of Intrinsic Achievement Of ILOs

35.00% was the most frequently occurring mark in the dataset or the lowest boundary level of the satisfactory level of the standard grading system. Any student belonging to this group might have the probability of having the “ILO_Rate” 35%.

4.2.4 Quantitative Analysis For Null Hypothesis 2 - Gender Vs. ILO_Rate

The null hypothesis “NH 2” was accepted as a considerable gap between the ILO_Rates of male students with the ILO_Rates of the female students.

	N	Mean	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
ILO_Rate	41	31.46	13.47	0	65
Valid N (listwise)	41				
Missing N (listwise)	0				

Figure 16: Male ILO_Rate

The table shown in “Figure 16” shows that the mean value of male students’ ILO_Rates is 31.46% while the following table shows the 36.88% as the mean value of ILO_Rates of female students. The difference between the two mean values is 5.42% that is not a considerable gap.

	N	Mean	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
ILO_Rate	69	36.88	11.48	10	60
Valid N (listwise)	69				
Missing N (listwise)	0				

Figure 17: Female ILO_Rate

Both girls and boys of grade 10 Buddhism subject learners are approximately at the same level of intrinsic achievement of ILOs, that is on the lower boundary of satisfactory level.

4.3 INFERENTIAL ANALYSIS

Chi-square statistical analysis comes into play in this research in quantitative data analysis stage by which the theories could be built.

4.3.1 Quantitative Analysis For Null Hypothesis 1 - Students' Attendance Vs. ILO_Rate

The following Chi-square test result showed that the hypothesis "NH 1" which states that the students' school attendance does not affect on their intrinsic achievement of ILOs, is true and correct.

	Value	df	symptoti Sig. (2- tailed)
Pearson Chi-Square	558.83	612	.939
Likelihood Ratio	325.15	612	1.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	.03	1	.862
N of Valid Cases	110		

Figure 18: Attendance Vs. ILO_Rate

“Figure 18” shows 0.939 as the p-value, 1.000 as the likelihood ratio, and 0.862 as the linear by linear association. Those values are less than 0.05 and hence the hypothesis “NH 1” becomes true. It says no significance relationship between the students’ school attendance rate and the ILO_Rate.

4.3.2 Quantitative Analysis For Null Hypothesis 3 - Term Test Marks Vs. ILO_Rate

The Chi-square test performed as an inferential statistical analysis to test the null hypothesis “NH3” which states that there is no significant relationship between students' term test marks and ILOs. Summary of the Chi-square test is shown in “Figure 19”.

	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Termtest_Mark x ILO_Rate	107	97.3%	3	2.7%	110	100.0%

Figure 19: Term Test Marks Vs. ILO_Rate Summary

Three students in the sample had not faced the term test and hence the total number of valid cases was 107.

	Value	df	symptoti Sig. (2- tailed)
Pearson Chi-Square	714.12	732	.675
Likelihood Ratio	366.08	732	1.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.88	1	.027
N of Valid Cases	107		

Figure 20: Marks, ILO_Rate

The p-value was 0.675. As it is greater than 0.05, it shows that the null hypothesis is correct. The likelihood ratio is also above the relevant value. Although the Linear by Linear association indicates 0.27, both the other values are above 0.05. Therefore, it is statistically proven that the level of students' intrinsic achievement of ILOs is independent from the marks scored at the term tests.

The histogram of term test marks is presented in "Figure 21".

Figure 21: Marks, Frequency

By comparing the histogram shown in “Figure 21” with the histogram of ILO_Rate, it was presented that the two components were not related to each other.

4.3.3 Analysis Of Null Hypothesis 4 – School Type Vs. ILO_Rate

It states that students’ desire to intrinsically reaching to ILOs does not depend on the type of school and the available various facilities and well-formed infrastructure. It was proven the result gained by comparing the mean of achieving ILOs of the semi-government college which has almost all the smart facilities, with the mean of the government school which is lack of smart technologies and even a considerable infrastructural development was also not found there. The schools were selected based on the stratified random sampling technique.

	N	Mean	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
ILO_Rate	51	35.78	12.42	0	60
Valid N (listwise)	51				
Missing N (listwise)	0				

Figure 22: Semi-government school ILO_Rate

“Figure 22” shows 35.78 as the mean of ILO_Rate of the semi-government school while the mean of the government school is set to 34.07 as shown in “Figure 23”.

	N	Mean	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
ILO_Rate	59	34.07	12.58	10	65
Valid N (listwise)	59				
Missing N (listwise)	0				

Figure 23: Government School ILO_Rate

The gap between the means of two types of schools is 1.71 which is a very small value.

4.4 QUALITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS

Except the statistically analysed hypotheses, all the other hypotheses were tested and qualitatively analysed.

4.4.1 Analysis Of Null Hypothesis 5 – Teaching Methodologies And Methods Vs.

ILO_Rate

Thematic analysis of Buddhism teachers revealed that the ILO_Rate was independent from the methodologies and methods of teaching as the teachers of both the schools had excerpts saying that they had used various but mostly similar teaching methods.

However, the mean value of ILO_Rates of each school was nearly similar. Thereby, this null hypothesis was accepted.

Following figure shows that the mean of ILO_Rate of the government school is 34.07% and the mean of semi-government school was 35.78%. Even the standard deviation values are also much closer. Standard deviation of the government school was 12.58 while the semi-government school held the value 12.42. Additionally, the maximum ILO_Rate of government school students was 65 while the other has got 60. There is not a considerable gap between the highest ILO_Rate values of the schools.

Thus, the hypothesis is both qualitatively and quantitatively proven.

4.4.2 Analysis Of Alternate Hypothesis 1 On “Having the Misleading Information In The Text Book”

Thematic analysis of 20th question in the students’ questionnaire is considered herein. The response presented in Excerpt 2 highlights a fundamental misunderstanding of the ontological nature of defilements and the epistemological framework of Vipassana meditation. This suggests a potential breakdown in the pedagogical process, either in the initial transmission of the core teachings or in subsequent reinforcement exercises. Additionally, the judgemental review ensures that the content on Vipassana meditation is not presented in a more pragmatic manner in the syllabus. Instead, it is taught just as a theory of getting liberated from misery but its mechanism. Furthermore, it doesn’t illustrate how a meditator understands the cause and effect theory, the four noble truths and the way of practising the eight fold path through Vipassana meditation. Thus, the hypothesis AH 1 is acceptable as true and correct.

4.4.3 Analysis Of Alternate Hypothesis 2 On “Classroom Content Vs. Understanding Pure Dhamma”

Accordingly the expert judgemental review, classroom material may be deficient in practical components, which means it fails to adequately relate Dhamma teachings to experiences or applications in real life, making it more difficult for students to fully understand and internalise the core of Dhamma beyond theoretical understanding. For example, useful tasks like guided meditation or reflections may be absent rather than just describing the idea of mindfulness. This can make it more difficult for pupils to use the Dhamma in their day-to-day activities. Hence this hypothesis is true.

4.4.4 Analysis Of Alternate Hypothesis 3 On “History And Literature Over The Pure Dhamma”

By referring to the expert judgemental review of 2nd issue of unit 01 illustrated in this documentation, the content does not promote the way to reach to the enlightenment clearly. Instead, it prioritizes the so-called Buddhist history and culture. However, as the Tipitaka says, the most vital use of Dhamma is nothing but practising Vipassana to get liberated from all the misery.

It is further clarified that the content is imbalanced accordingly the 5th theme generated from the excerpts given by the Buddhism teachers while they were being interviewed.

Due to these two evidence, the hypothesis AH 3 becomes true.

4.4.5 Analysis Of Alternate Hypothesis 4 On “Exam-centric Syllabus”

Accordingly the theme 1 developed from the excerpts of Buddhism teachers, it is proven that the syllabus tends to deliver the content in an exam-oriented manner by its

nature. The thematic analysis of teachers' perspectives on the syllabus proves that the alternate hypothesis AH 4 is correct.

4.4.6 Analysis Of Alternate Hypothesis 5 On “Lack Of Teachers’ Vipassana Practice”

Accordingly the 6th theme developed from Buddhism teachers' excerpts, they do not practise Vipassana as a habitual action and hence their practical knowledge is not at a satisfactory level to guide a student through the phases of “*arya magga*” – the path to “*Nibbana*” – the everlasting happiness. Teachers have failed to train their students in mindfulness and concentration too. Then, this hypothesis is true and correct according to the 6th theme developed in the research process.

4.4.7 Analysis Of Alternate Hypothesis 6 On “Teachers’ Pali Knowledge”

Accordingly the expert judgement review on the 1st issue of the 2nd unit, Buddhism teachers should have sufficient knowledge on understanding Pali and continuous association of the Tipitaka, to clarify the matters discussed in Dhamma, not only in the textbook, but also in any other material. Therefore, the students fail to reach the expected outcomes. Without this practice, teachers fail to validate the content. Thus, this hypothesis is true.

4.4.8 Analysis Of Alternate Hypothesis 7 On “Teachers’ Attempts To Study The Tipitaka”

Through the excerpts and the 10th initial code in thematic analysis of teachers' perspectives on the grade 10 Buddhism syllabus, all the teachers in the sample said that they never follow Tipitaka at all, in their day-to-day life. It directly affects to their failure of validation and verification of the syllabus and textbooks. Thus, the hypothesis becomes acceptable as true and correct.

4.4.9 Analysis Of Alternate Hypothesis 8 On Mismatching Between The Content And ILOs

As the experts' review pinpoints that the content of the Buddhism textbook based on the syllabus of grade 10, does not align with the expected outcomes. As a counter example to prove this, the review of unit 1 is taken. It says about the “*pancha maha vilokana*” but it cannot be done by anybody except the Lord Buddha. By teaching the matter, students are advised to take it as a model to be applied in their life. It is not pragmatic as that kind of super power cannot be suddenly developed by any student. Thus, the hypothesis becomes a true and valid notion.

4.5 SUMMARY OF CHAPTER FOUR

The evaluation of the Grade 10 Buddhism syllabus in Sri Lankan schools reveals a complex interplay of factors influencing the attainment of Intended Learning Outcomes. Quantitative analysis indicates a moderate level of ILO achievement, with no significant differences based on gender, attendance, term test marks, or school type. However, qualitative analysis suggests potential pedagogical shortcomings, including a theoretical emphasis in the textbooks, a lack of practical components in classroom instruction, a disproportionate focus on history over Dhamma, and a curriculum that prioritizes examination preparation. Additionally, teachers' limited Vipassana practice, insufficient Pali knowledge, and infrequent use of the Tipitaka may further hinder effective teaching and learning. These findings highlight the need for a comprehensive review of the syllabus and a focus on practical, experiential learning to foster a deeper understanding of Dhamma principles.

CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSION

5.1 INTRODUCTION TO DISCUSSION ON FINDINGS

This chapter penetrates through the findings discussed in the previous chapter, in detail. It further explores the broader implications, the place occupying within the existing literature, and the influence of finding the degree of intrinsic achievement of the ILOs in grade 10 Buddhism students' mind, as per the research objectives – assessing the existing Buddhism syllabus, examining the students' perception on the syllabus, identifying the factors affecting the intrinsic achievement of ILOs, and proposing the recommendations for teaching Buddhism in schools.

5.2 LINKING FINDINGS TO THE RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

A critical analysis of the Grade 10 Buddhism syllabus in Sri Lankan schools was undertaken in Chapter Four of this study. This investigation, employing a mixed-methods approach, sought to examine the alignment of the syllabus with its intended learning outcomes (ILOs). Both quantitative and qualitative analyses were conducted to identify strengths and weaknesses in both the syllabus content and its implementation. The quantitative analysis, encompassing descriptive, inferential, and correlational statistics, was complemented by a qualitative analysis involving thematic analysis and expert judgment. The following synthesis of findings is presented in alignment with the study's research objectives and methodologies.

5.3 KEY FINDINGS

The pivotal findings came from both qualitative and quantitative analyses.

5.3.1 Discussion On Intrinsic Achievement of ILOs

The quantitative analysis of the intrinsic achievement of Intended Learning Outcomes (ILO_Rate) reveals critical insights into the effectiveness of the syllabus in fostering deep engagement and mastery among students.

The calculated mean ILO_Rate of 34.86% situates the overall performance within the "Weak" category as per the established grading standards, underscoring a pervasive limitation in the attainment of the intended educational outcomes.

Further, the median value of 35% aligns with the lower boundary of the "Satisfactory" classification, indicating that the majority of students marginally meet the basic expectations of syllabus comprehension and application.

The modal value, also at 35%, reinforces this trend, highlighting a concentration of student performance at the threshold level, thereby reflecting a significant challenge in surpassing minimal achievement levels.

Moreover, the observed standard deviation of 12.47 illustrates a moderate degree of variability in performance, suggesting heterogeneity in individual capabilities and engagement with the syllabus content.

Collectively, these findings illuminate the critical need for pedagogical interventions aimed at enhancing students' intrinsic motivation and their capacity to internalize and apply the theoretical constructs of the syllabus.

5.3.2 Discussion On Null Hypothesis Testing

The null hypothesis testing provided compelling insights into the factors influencing the intrinsic attainment of Intended Learning Outcomes (ILO_Rate), with the analyses revealing an absence of statistically significant relationships across key variables. Gender-based performance differences were found to be negligible, as female students demonstrated a marginally higher mean ILO_Rate of 36.88% compared to their male

counterparts at 31.46%. Despite this slight variation, both cohorts remained within the lower bounds of the "Satisfactory" achievement level, thereby indicating that gender does not substantially influence ILO attainment.

Similarly, the relationship between attendance rates and ILO_Rate was statistically insignificant, as evidenced by chi-square analysis, suggesting that the frequency of classroom participation has limited direct impact on intrinsic academic performance.

Furthermore, no correlation was identified between term test marks and ILO achievement, thereby indicating that traditional assessment metrics are not predictive of students' capacity to internalize and actualize syllabus objectives.

Finally, an evaluation of school type revealed a negligible difference in mean ILO_Rates between students from semi-government schools (35.78%) and those from government schools (34.07%). This finding underscores the minimal influence of institutional infrastructure and resources on fostering the intrinsic mastery of learning outcomes.

Collectively, these results highlight the multifaceted and complex nature of educational achievement, suggesting the need for a deeper exploration of underlying motivational and cognitive factors that drive student success.

5.3.3 Discussion On Misalignment Between Textbook Content And Practical Dhamma

A critical misalignment is evident between the prescribed textbook content and the practical application of Dhamma, undermining the potential for holistic educational outcomes. The syllabus predominantly emphasizes the historical and cultural dimensions of Buddhism, privileging a didactic exploration of Buddhist heritage over actionable insights into personal and spiritual growth.

Central teachings such as the Four Noble Truths and the Eightfold Path are primarily confined to theoretical expositions, devoid of the experiential methodologies necessary for their integration into daily life.

Notably, transformative practices such as Vipassana meditation and mindfulness, which serve as cornerstone techniques for internalizing and operationalizing Buddhist principles, are conspicuously absent from the curriculum. This theoretical-practical divide restricts students' ability to engage with the Dhamma as a living philosophy, thereby limiting their capacity to apply its teachings in cultivating ethical, mental, and emotional well-being.

The expert review exposed 11 issues found in the units – 1, 2,5,8 and 14. The unit 2 has 5 issues, unit 1 has 3 issues while the other three units have 1 issue in each unit. They are misconceptions and misleading information. In the previous chapter, they have been elaborately reported.

5.3.4 Teacher Competence And Pedagogical Practices

The pedagogical efficacy within the context of Buddhist education is significantly constrained by limitations in teacher competence and instructional methodologies. While educators employ a range of teaching strategies, these are predominantly exam-centric, prioritizing rote memorization over fostering a deeper, intrinsic understanding of Buddhist principles.

A notable deficiency lies in the teachers' personal engagement with Vipassana meditation practices, which impairs their ability to effectively guide students in cultivating mindfulness and concentration—key aspects of practical Dhamma application.

Furthermore, the limited proficiency of educators in Pali, the canonical language of Buddhist scriptures, inhibits their capacity to critically interpret and validate textbook content against primary sources such as the Tipitaka. The lack of consistent and meaningful engagement with the Tipitaka further diminishes the authenticity, depth, and doctrinal integrity of instructional delivery, thereby restricting students' exposure to the foundational texts that form the cornerstone of Buddhist philosophy and practice.

5.3.5 Exam-centric Nature Of The Syllabus

The syllabus, characterized by its pronounced exam-centric orientation, prioritizes the acquisition of knowledge and skills primarily for the purpose of academic assessment. This approach, while potentially effective in fostering rote learning and test-taking abilities, inadvertently marginalizes the intrinsic, practical, and spiritual dimensions of Buddhist teachings.

Consequently, students may emerge from their studies with a superficial understanding of the Dharma, lacking the profound insights and transformative experiences that are the hallmark of genuine Buddhist practice.

5.3.6 Feedback On Content Delivery

Student feedback reveals a pronounced disconnect between the theoretical constructs of Buddhist education and their practical applicability in fostering a lived understanding of Dhamma.

Learners consistently reported challenges in bridging the gap between the abstract conceptualization of Buddhist teachings and their implementation in daily life. This disjunction is exacerbated by the absence of experiential learning components within the classroom environment.

Specifically, the lack of structured activities such as guided meditation precludes opportunities for students to internalize and embody core principles like mindfulness and insight, thereby limiting their capacity to engage with the transformative aspects of Dhamma beyond the confines of academic discourse.

5.4 IMPLICATIONS OF FINDINGS

1. Curriculum Revision

A comprehensive revision of the curriculum is imperative to bridge the gap between theoretical expositions of Buddhist teachings and their practical applications. Central to this revision is the integration of experiential learning opportunities that emphasize the cultivation of mindfulness and reflective practices. These elements, when embedded alongside traditional theoretical content, can significantly enhance students' capacity to internalize and operationalize the Dhamma in their lived experiences. Additionally, the inclusion of illustrative examples and real-life case studies serves to contextualize abstract teachings, thereby demonstrating their contemporary relevance and fostering a deeper, more pragmatic engagement with Buddhist principles. Such a restructured curriculum aims to cultivate a holistic understanding that extends beyond rote learning, enabling students to embody the transformative ethos of the Dhamma.

2. Teacher Training

To elevate the efficacy of pedagogical practices, a robust framework for teacher training must be established, emphasizing both the practical and theoretical dimensions of Buddhist education. First, structured training programs in Vipassana meditation and mindfulness should be introduced, equipping educators with experiential knowledge and practical proficiency essential for fostering a transformative learning environment. Such training not only enhances the authenticity

of instruction but also empowers teachers to serve as exemplars of the principles they impart. Concurrently, specialized courses in Pali language and Tipitaka studies are indispensable for augmenting teachers' capabilities to interpret, contextualize, and deliver content with greater depth and accuracy. By strengthening these foundational competencies, teachers can bridge the existing gap between canonical knowledge and its practical transmission, thereby fostering an enriched educational experience that aligns with the curriculum's intended outcomes.

3. Assessment Reform

To align assessment practices with the overarching objectives of Buddhist education, a comprehensive reform in evaluation methodologies is imperative. Current assessment frameworks, predominantly centred on theoretical knowledge, must be recalibrated to emphasize the practical understanding and application of Buddhist principles. This entails the integration of evaluative mechanisms that gauge students' ability to internalize and enact Dhamma in real-life contexts, such as reflective journaling, mindfulness exercises, and scenario-based problem-solving. By prioritizing experiential and competency-based assessments, this reformed approach seeks to transcend rote memorization, fostering a deeper engagement with the transformative potential of Buddhist teachings. Such a paradigm shift not only enhances the authenticity of student evaluations but also ensures that assessments serve as a meaningful conduit for achieving the intrinsic learning outcomes envisioned by the curriculum.

4. Resource Accessibility

The development of comprehensive and contextually relevant educational resources is a critical component of fostering an enriched learning environment for Buddhist

studies. To bridge the gap between theoretical exposition and practical application, the creation of supplementary materials that prioritize actionable insights into the Eightfold Path and other core teachings is essential. These resources should provide structured exercises, case studies, and guided reflections that enable students to internalize and apply Buddhist principles in their daily lives.

5. Student-centred Learning

A paradigm shift towards student-centred learning is imperative for fostering deeper engagement and intrinsic understanding of Buddhist principles. By prioritizing interactive and experiential pedagogical strategies, the educational framework can evolve to accommodate diverse learning styles and promote active participation. Organizing Vipassana meditation sessions offer students opportunities to explore and critically analyse Buddhist teachings, and the development of interpretive skills. Furthermore, integrating community service projects aligned with Buddhist principles creates a bridge between theoretical knowledge and its practical application, enabling students to embody core values such as compassion, ethical conduct, and altruism in real-world contexts. These methodologies not only enhance cognitive and affective learning outcomes but also nurture a holistic appreciation of Dhamma as a lived experience, thereby aligning educational practices with the transformative goals of Buddhist education.

5.5 SUMMARY OF CHAPTER FIVE

The quantitative analysis of the intrinsic achievement of Intended Learning Outcomes (ILO_Rate) in Grade 10 Buddhism highlights a systemic deficiency in the attainment of intended educational objectives. This deficiency underscores the urgent need for a pedagogical paradigm shift, prioritizing intrinsic learning outcomes over exam-centric

approaches. By addressing critical gaps in teacher competency, syllabus content, and instructional strategies, it is possible to significantly enhance students' capacity to internalize and apply Buddhist teachings in their lives.

CHAPTER SIX: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 CONCLUSION

Gender, school infrastructure, facilities provided for the currently active teaching-learning process in schools, access to the cutting edge technologies, teaching methodology and methods, students' daily attendance, students' term test marks, students' gender do not affect at a considerable degree to guide the students towards their intrinsic achievement of the intended learning outcomes defined in the grade 10 local Buddhism syllabus delivered in schools in Sri Lanka and hence it is clear that either the ILOs defined in the syllabus must be updated or the content must be restructured and enriched with pure Dhamma by integrating the unique practical technique of getting liberated from all the misery, or "Vipassana meditation" that guides the follower towards the everlasting happiness as taught in Tipitaka which is to be given to both the students and teachers to study it as a habitual action. Lack of proper teacher training, lack of knowledge on Pali language, limited access to the recommended texts especially the "*Buddha Jayanthi Thripitaka*", unavailability of Vipassana practitioners, very less number of research conducted in this dimension in the field are identified as the causes for having high failure rate of achieving the intended learning outcomes intrinsically.

6.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Syllabus and Curriculum Reform
 - Revise ILOs: The Intended Learning Outcomes in the Grade 10 local Buddhism syllabus should be critically reviewed to ensure they align with the core principles of Buddhism and promote the development of students' spiritual and moral character.

- Curriculum Enrichment: The syllabus should be enriched with practical applications of Buddhist teachings, including Vipassana meditation, to enhance students' understanding and personal growth.
 - Integration of Dhamma: The unique practical technique of Vipassana meditation should be integrated into the curriculum as a core component, providing students with a direct path to liberation from suffering and the attainment of lasting happiness.
2. Teacher Training and Development
- Comprehensive Teacher Training: Implement comprehensive teacher training programs that equip educators with the knowledge and skills necessary to effectively teach Buddhism, including Pali language proficiency and the practice of Vipassana meditation.
 - Access to Resources: Provide teachers with access to essential resources, such as the "Buddha Jayanthi Thripitaka" and other recommended texts, to deepen their understanding of Buddhist teachings.
 - Collaboration with Vipassana Practitioners: Facilitate collaboration between teachers and experienced Vipassana practitioners to enhance their teaching methodologies and personal practice.
3. Research and Innovation
- Promote Research: Encourage research in the field of Buddhist education to identify effective teaching strategies, assess the impact of Vipassana meditation on student learning, and inform future curriculum development.

- **Data-Driven Decision Making:** Utilize data on student performance and engagement to inform evidence-based decision-making and continuous improvement of the curriculum and teaching practices.
4. **Student Support and Engagement**
- **Create Supportive Learning Environments:** Foster a positive and conducive learning environment that encourages students to explore their spiritual potential and practice mindfulness.
 - **Promote Student Engagement:** Implement innovative teaching methods, such as interactive discussions, group activities, and meditation sessions, to enhance student engagement and motivation.
 - **Provide Guidance and Counselling:** Offer guidance and counselling services to help students overcome challenges and develop their spiritual and emotional well-being.

By implementing these recommendations, the effectiveness of Buddhist education in Sri Lankan schools can be significantly improved and empowered so as to students to lead meaningful and fulfilling lives.

6.3 SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

1. Impact Analysis of Curriculum Reforms

The impact of revised “Intended Learning Outcomes” and enriched curriculum on students' understanding and intrinsic achievement of Buddhist principles is to be evaluated, and the effectiveness of integrating Vipassana meditation and practical Dhamma teachings in improving students' spiritual and moral growth is to be assessed.

2. Teacher Training Efficacy

Studies have to be conducted on the outcomes of comprehensive teacher training programs, including their proficiency in Pali language and the application of Vipassana in classrooms. The correlation between teacher training quality and students' intrinsic engagement with Buddhist teachings has also to be analysed.

3. Role of Vipassana Meditation

The direct impact of Vipassana meditation practice on students' emotional well-being, concentration, and intrinsic alignment with the teachings of Buddhism is to be investigated. Traditional teaching methods are to be compared with meditation-based approaches to evaluate differences in achieving ILOs.

4. Access to Resources

The accessibility and usage of core texts such as the "Buddha Jayanthi Thripitaka" by teachers and students are to be further studied. Digital solutions and translations for increasing access to Pali texts and Buddhist scriptures are also to be explored.

5. Cultural and Contextual Relevance

The cultural and social barriers that may impede the effectiveness of the current Buddhism syllabus are examined. The local context that influences students' reception of Buddhist teachings and their practical applications is to be further explored.

6. Longitudinal Studies

Longitudinal studies may be conducted to track the long-term effects of Buddhist education reforms on students' lives, including their ethical behavior, decision-making, and personal fulfilment.

7. Interdisciplinary Research

Interdisciplinary research may be conducted by collaborating with fields such as psychology, education, and theology to study the psychological and cognitive impacts

of mindfulness and meditation practices on young learners. Additionally, research may be conducted on the integration of technology in teaching Buddhism, such as meditation apps or interactive platforms for learning Pali.

8. Comparative Studies

The effectiveness of the Sri Lankan Buddhist curriculum is to be compared with similar programs in other countries, such as Myanmar or Thailand, which emphasize practical applications of Buddhist teachings.

9. Policy and Implementation Analysis

The challenges in implementing proposed reforms at policy and administrative levels are to be studied, and the scalability of Vipassana-based education and its integration into the national syllabus are also to be further analysed in future.

REFERENCES

- Chancey, J. B., Hong, J. Y., & Heddy, B. C. (2019). Transformative Experience in Buddhism: A Case Study. *Journal of Transformative Learning*, 6(2).
<https://jotl.uco.edu/index.php/jotl/article/view/266/163>
- Chumsukon, M., & Ruangsang, N. (2021). Review of international geographical education integration of research based learning and community learning resources to enhance analytical thinking skills of pre-service teachers. *Review of International Geographical Education*, 11(5).
<https://doi.org/10.33403/rigeo.11.05.156>
- De Silva, C. R. (2019). The education of buddhist monks in sri lanka: a historical review and some suggestions for reform. *Sri Lanka Journal of the Humanities*, 42(1-2), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.4038/sljh.v42i1-2.7253>
- Dipobhasadhamma, V. (2023). Handbook for living the noble eightfold path. *Handbook for Living: The Eightfold Noble Path*.
https://www.academia.edu/112090273/Handbook_for_Living_The_Noble_Eightfold_Path?uc-g-sw=43292517
- Gleick, J., & Dyson, F. J. (1992). Genius: The life and science of richard feynman. *Physics Today*, 45(11), 87–87. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2809877>
- Gyeltshen, D., & Lopez, M. (2021). So Old and Yet So New: Buddhist Education and the Monastic Curriculum in Contemporary Bhutan *. In *Bhutanstudies*.
https://www.bhutanstudies.org.bt/publicationFiles/JBS/JBS%2045/JBS_45_01.pdf
- Luaensutthi, A., & Sangsawang, T. (2023). Data analytics of online lessons in social studies and buddhism: Enhancing dhamma teaching and tripitaka

- understanding among teachers and students. *Journal of Applied Data Sciences*, 4(3), 200–212. <https://doi.org/10.47738/jads.v4i3.125>
- Massoudi, M. (2010). Learning and teaching ethics through stories: “A few examples from the buddhist tradition.” *Creative Education*, 01(01), 18–24. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ce.2010.11004>
- ministry, education. (2023). *Performance of candidates examination 2022*. https://doenets.lk/images/resources/STAT/2022_OL_POC_1702311346658.pdf
- Nelson, J., & Yang, Y. (2021). World religions in religious education in northern ireland: A policy implementation analysis using strategic action field theory. *Religion & Education*, 49(1), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15507394.2021.2009303>
- Pugh, K. J. (2011). Transformative experience: An integrative construct in the spirit of deweyan pragmatism. *Educational Psychologist*, 46(2), 107–121. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2011.558817>
- Pugh, K. J., Bergstrom, C. M., Heddy, B. C., & Krob, K. E. (2017). Supporting deep engagement: The teaching for transformative experiences in science model. *The Journal of Experimental Education*, 85(4), 629–657. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220973.2016.1277333>
- Sik, H., & Wu, W. (2015). Title the importance of the buddhist teaching on three kinds of knowing: In a school-based contemplative education program. In *core.ac.uk*. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/38068284.pdf>
- Srinok, S., Wongsuwan, N., Buppapan, S., Widesbrommakun, P., Thongdee, V., & Ruangsang, N. (2021). Buddhism and Thai educational system. *Linguistics and*

Culture Review, 5(S1), 1335–1342.

<https://doi.org/10.21744/lingcure.v5ns1.1635>

Wijayarathna, W. K. M., Abhayasundere, P., & Jayaweera, P. M. (2020). Dialectic nature of digital culture: theoretical analysis of evolutionary “digital Buddhism” of social media debate. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 8(2), 69. <https://doi.org/10.4038/ijms.v8i2.141>

APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Questions In The Questionnaire, Contents And Targeted ILO.

Table 13: Appendix 1 - Questions And ILOs With Content

Content	ILO	Question for Evaluation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social leadership, • religious mission, • charity, alms-giving, • devotional service, • sermons, • participation in weddings, funerals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explains the social mission of “Sangha Ratna”. • It is accepted that they should contribute to the existence of monks. • Devotees associate with temples 	<p>1) You have learned that setting auspicious moments for wedding occasions by Buddhist monks is a good social mission.</p> <p>1. It leads to the progress of Buddhist monks’ society.</p> <p>2. It leads to the decline of Buddhist monks’ society.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review the virtues of Triple Gems, learn from them, and act accordingly. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Worshipping the triple gems daily. • Demonstrates religious faith. 	<p>2) Do you observe the five precepts (“<i>pancha seela</i>”) almost every day when school is not held?</p> <p>1. yes 2. no</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to “<i>Samata</i>” Meditation, Personalities, Four Poses, Precedents to meditation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make meditation a lifelong habit. • Describe “<i>Samata</i>” meditation uniquely. • It is accepted that the mind can be reconciled by increasing “<i>Samata</i>” meditation. 	<p>3) Do you do “<i>Samata</i>” meditation daily at home?</p> <p>1. Yes 2. No</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to “<i>Samata</i>” meditation, Personalities, Four Poses, Precedents to meditation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practising “<i>Samata</i>” meditation in correct posture. 	<p>4) If you practice “<i>Samata</i>” meditation, do you already have a teacher of meditation to give advice on it?</p> <p>1. Yes 2.No</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ven. Welivita Sangharaja Thero and King Dutu Gemunu. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explains the social mission of Ven. Welivita Sangharaja Thero and King Dutu Gemunu. 	<p>5) As you think, was defeating the just and righteous king Elara militarily by the king Dutu Gemunu fair?</p> <p>1. Yes 2. No</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The couplet of stanzas "Acharitva Brahmachariyang" and the "Dhamma 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do the right work at the right time. 	<p>6) Is it your habit to return to the classroom before the school recess bell rings?</p> <p>1. yes 2. no</p>

<p>Pada" stanzas "Uttanavatho Satimato" and their meaning.</p>		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Buddhist teachings related to health, teachings related to Vinaya Pitaka. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Works with time management 	<p>7) Could you stop coming to school late just because you studied Buddhism at school? 1. yes 2. no</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of common property, interfaith association, pious work, new year festival rituals, dealing with calamities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rituals explain. • Lists measures to be followed to protect common property. 	<p>8) Do you have some unnecessarily drawn doodles on your desk? 1. yes 2. no</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Buddhist teachings related to health, teachings related to Vinaya Pitaka. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Makes a suitable schedule to make the educational activities successful. 	<p>9) Do you study at home according to the schedule because you have learned Buddhism? 1. yes 2. no</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Benefits of moral practice “<i>sila</i>”. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respecting elders, leading a virtuous life 	<p>10) When your parents find out that you play computer games on a daily basis, do you stop immediately when your parents</p>

		warn you to stop immediately? 1. yes 2. no
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “<i>sadisa namaskara</i>” in “<i>Sigalowada sutta</i>” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Takes care to fulfil own duties. 	11) When the teachers advise you to study the subjects taught daily, do you do it with high priority?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leaving the castle, experience of “<i>sathara pera nimithi</i>”, birth of prince Siddarta, having education. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explains the special events connected with the birth of the "<i>bodisatva</i>". 	12) One of the special events associated with the birth of Bosat, walking on lotus flowers and reciting the stanza "Aggo Hamsmin Lokassa" really happened as you think?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leaving the castle, experience of “<i>sathara pera nimithi</i>”, birth of prince Siddarta, having education. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrates patience in the face of problems 	13) If a student in your class has been making various insulting accusations against you for months, and you complain to the teachers about it, but they ignore your complaint, and the student continues to harass you, will you at some point resort to hitting him? Or will you resort to tolerating his troubles until the end of your school life? 1. hitting 2. tolerating

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review of the Four Noble Truths 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clearly explains the Four Noble Truths in order. • Solves problems analytically. • Acts with a great sense of life. 	<p>14) Although the Four Noble Truths are presented in order as suffering, the cause of suffering, the cessation of suffering, and the path to the cessation of suffering, some argue that the cessation of suffering, or the Third Noble Truth, occurs after the path to the cessation of suffering has been followed, so the Four Noble Truths are as follows in order: suffering, the cause of suffering, the path to the cessation of suffering, the cessation of suffering. Do you agree with this statement?</p> <p>1. Agree 2. Disagree</p> <p>Give reasons.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • lotus-like life of the Buddha 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Works for purity of character. • Explains what a lotus life is. 	<p>15) Has studying the lotus-like life of the Buddha helped in the purification of your character?</p> <p>1. yes 2. no</p> <p>State when it happened.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Couplet "acharitwa" 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gets the maximum use 	<p>16) Even if you learn the couplet</p>

<p>brahma chariyan" and the dhammapada stanza "uttanawato satimato" and their meanings</p>	<p>out of time.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work on time. 	<p>"acharitwa brahma chariyan" and the dhammapada stanza "uttanawato satimato" and their meanings, could you be able to develop your time management skills?</p> <p>1. yes 2. no</p> <p>Give reasons.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Karma, karma, types, karmic consequences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When performing an action, one is concerned about the good and the bad. • Live a virtuous life. 	<p>17) Since you learned about karma and karmic consequences in the twelfth lesson of the tenth grade, are there times when you thought about making a mistake in life and did not do it?</p> <p>1. yes 2. no</p> <p>Describe such a situation.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevant teachings in the Vinaya Pitaka 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spending leisure time productively. 	<p>18) Name two things you like to do at home during your free time.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Venerable Weliwita Sangharaja Thera, King Dutu Gemunu. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Looking for role models. 	<p>19) You have learned that role models such as the Venerable Sangharaja Thera and King Dutu Gemunu, who established the</p>

		<p>Dhamma, have carried out a series of missions for the perpetuation of Buddhism. Accordingly, have you been informed by the Sri Lankan government over the past few decades?</p> <p>1. yes 2. no</p> <p>If you are aware, please mention two such facts.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vipassana Meditation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explain how to practice Vipassana meditation. • Accept that Vipassana meditation leads to the realization of “Nirvana”. • Prepares a guide on the steps to follow when practising Vipassana meditation. • Analytical views of daily life events. • Adapt change. 	<p>20) Explain the mechanism by which defilements are reduced through Vipassana meditation.</p>

Appendix 2: Questions Thrown When Students Were Being Interviewed.

Question 1:

1. Do you accept astrology?
2. Is it appropriate for a monk to use it to meet the needs of a layperson, as you interpret it?
3. What do you think are the things that monks do today that are incompatible with monastic life?

Question 2:

1. When a mosquito bites you, do you unconsciously squash or kill the mosquito?

Question 3:

1. Do you practice meditation in your free time?
2. How many hours is that in a week?

Question 4:

1. Do you seek advice from a meditation teacher?

Question 5:

1. As you have learned, Elara was a just and righteous ruler. Do you think it was just for King Dutu Gemunu to kill such a righteous ruler?

Question 6:

1. When the bell rings at the end of school interval, you return to the classroom as soon as possible,
 1. Because it has to be done according to school rules.
 2. Because I am very passionate about learning the next subject.
 3. Because the teacher is punishing.
 4. For several reasons above.

5. For none of the above reasons

Question 7:

1. Are you trying to avoid coming to school late because you are studying Buddhism in grade ten or for some other reason?
2. Explain.

Question 8:

1. Do you like to draw some unwanted doodles on your desk?
2. Has it become a habit of yours?
3. Do you think it's a bad habit that should be abandoned?
4. But have you failed to give it up yet?

Question 9:

1. Do you use a schedule in any way to structure your studies?
2. Do you believe that such a schedule should be maintained?
3. What lesson in the grade 10 Buddhism textbook can you cite as the one that inspired you to create such a timetable?
4. Can't you recognize such a lesson in your Buddhism textbook?

Question 10:

1. Do you play computer games behind your parents' backs?
2. How many hours a day do you usually play computer games?

Question 11:

1. Do you complete the lessons taught to you by your teachers at school every day?
2. How much time do you usually spend studying at home each day?

Question 12:

1. Can you decide without any doubt that modern science is correct as you think?
2. Do you agree that Buddhism is almost completely compatible with modern science?
3. It is reported that prince Siddhartha walked on the lotus flowers that is said to have occurred on the day of his birth. In the scientific investigation of Buddhism, do you believe this as a true incident occurred in the real world?

Question 13:

1. When you are being bullied by a classmate, do you sometimes feel tempted to attack that student, thinking that you can stop it?

Question 14:

1. Do you accept the order in which the Four Noble Truths are taught in your curriculum?
2. On what basis do you think that is?

Question 15:

1. Have you studied the way of life of the Buddha?
2. Have you ever benefited from it in your life?
3. If so, what are they?

Question 16:

1. If the verses “*acharithwa brahma chariyan*” and “*uttanavato satimato*” have had any impact on your life, please describe them now.

Question 17:

1. “If you do a good deed, only good will come back to you.” Is this statement true?

Question 18:

1. Do you engage in activities such as using mobile phones, watching adult-only movies, or using drugs to pass your time?

Question 19:

1. Are you aware of the life stories of great men of our time?
2. So whose life story is that?
3. If you have such a life story, what examples have you taken from it?
4. Has not it been possible to obtain such an example so far?

Question 20:

1. Have you learned how to do Vipassana meditation?
2. Explain how.
3. Have you experienced in practice that it reduces impurities?
4. Explain how it destroys defilements.